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Draft Bisphenol A (BPA) hazard assessment protocol

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Abstract

To ensure an efficient, transparent and methodologically rigorous re-assessment of the safety for consumers of bisphenol A (BPA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has undertaken the task to develop a protocol detailing *a priori* the approach and methodology for performing BPA hazard identification and characterisation. The general aim of this hazard assessment will be to assess whether the new scientific evidence (published from 2013 onwards and not previously appraised by EFSA) still supports the current temporary Tolerable Daily Intake (t-TDI) for BPA of 4 µg/kg bw per day. In line with the principles highlighted in the EFSA project on promoting methods for evidence use in scientific assessments (Prometheus, <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/4121>), the protocol states upfront and in detail the methods and/or the criteria that will be used in the planned BPA re-evaluation for data collection, study inclusion, evidence appraisal and integration. To pursue the goal of openness, this draft protocol will be subjected to a web-based public consultation and will be presented publicly in a stakeholder event. All the relevant comments and feedback received through these procedures will be considered and included in the revision of the protocol which will be implemented in its final form in the next BPA re-evaluation.

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¹ by the EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids (CEF)

DRAFT

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51 **1. Introduction**

52 The development of this protocol detailing the strategy for the hazard assessment of BPA
53 (hazard identification and characterisation) was initiated as an EFSA self-task, as
54 described in mandate M-2016-0207 (EFSA-Q-2016-00673). This was triggered by the
55 need to ensure that the EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and
56 Processing Aids (CEF Panel) is prepared for the upcoming re-evaluation of the safety for
57 consumers of BPA, once the results of the two-year US National Toxicology Programme
58 (NTP)/ Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) toxicity study become available in
59 2017/2018.

60 After the initiation of this work, EFSA received an additional mandate from the European
61 Commission (EC, EFSA-Q-2016-00635) to re-evaluate the safety for consumers of BPA,
62 which requires setting-up a BPA hazard assessment protocol as a first step.

63 These two independent mandates from EFSA and the European Commission are reported
64 in Sections 1.1 and 1.2, respectively.

65 **1.1. Background and Terms of Reference as provided by EFSA**

66 This work aims to ensure that the CEF Panel will be fully prepared to engage in a re-
67 evaluation of the safety for consumers of BPA (to set a full TDI) when the two-year
68 ongoing NTP study report becomes available in 2017. In its latest risk assessment
69 published in 2015, the CEF Panel reduced and set the TDI for BPA on a temporary basis
70 to account for uncertainties related to possible BPA effects at low doses on mammary
71 gland, reproductive, neurological, immune and/or metabolic systems, thus committing to
72 a re-evaluation of the TDI in light of the new data available. Although the NTP study
73 design covers all the most controversial issues, at the same time the extensive body of
74 new literature that is being published on BPA cannot be ignored, and this is deemed
75 appropriate for the applicability of a defined protocol in the context of the EFSA
76 PROMoting METHods for Evidence Use in Science (Prometheus) project (EFSA, 2015) .

77 The Assessment and Methodological support (AMU) Unit will assist in the methodology
78 and design of the protocol to be followed for the risk assessment. The sensitivity of the
79 topic at EU level would also benefit from an early involvement of some Member States
80 and/ or sister agencies.

81 The Food Ingredients & Packaging (FIP) Unit should ensure that the CEF Panel is fully
82 prepared to engage in a re-evaluation of the safety for consumers of BPA (setting a full
83 TDI) in compliance with the principles of Prometheus, when the two-year ongoing NTP
84 study report becomes available in 2017.

85 **Terms of reference**

86 To ensure preparedness in view of an upcoming evaluation in 2017, the FIP Unit is
87 invited to develop a protocol detailing the strategy for the hazard assessment of BPA
88 (hazard identification and characterisation) to be endorsed by the CEF Panel. The
89 protocol should also define *a priori* how the new evidence will be appraised for relevance
90 and reliability.

91 **1.2. Background and Terms of Reference as provided by the European** 92 **Commission**

93 EFSA has accepted a mandate upon request from the European Commission to perform a re-
94 evaluation of the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs and
95 protocol for the risk assessment strategy. The background to this mandate, as provided by the EC is
96 the following:

97 *"In 2015 you published an opinion setting out a new temporary Tolerable Daily Intake (t-TDI) for BPA.*
98 *Recently you received a request for the re-evaluation of this TDI from the Dutch authorities. Following*
99 *the new temporary TDI and pending the outcome of the discussions following the Dutch request, the*

100 *Commission plans to hold a vote on a draft Commission Regulation in the Standing Committee on*
101 *Plants, Animals, Food and Feed. This draft Regulation would lower the specific migration limit for BPA*
102 *from plastic food contact materials and would apply the same limit to food contact varnishes and*
103 *coatings.*

104 *The on-going discussions however highlight the need of additional information on various toxicological*
105 *aspects. The study which was notified to EFSA by the Dutch authorities concerns the potential effects*
106 *of BPA on the immune system. However more data are needed about other toxicological endpoints of*
107 *BPA, including those relating to the mammary gland, reproductive, metabolic, and neurological*
108 *systems. In your 2015 opinion which set the t-TDI, these endpoints were taken into account by*
109 *means of an uncertainty evaluation.*

110 *In the mentioned opinion, EFSA assigned the temporary status to the TDI in recognition of the*
111 *partially uncertain toxicology and because of its awareness of ongoing studies addressing the*
112 *uncertainties. Therefore it is appropriate that the risk assessment you published in 2015 is refined.*

113 *It is essential that well-defined and transparent scientific criteria concerning the selection of the new*
114 *scientific studies are laid down in advance of the re-evaluation. This would enable a comprehensive*
115 *assessment of all relevant and adequate studies, and avoid the need to react to ad-hoc requests*
116 *concerning individual scientific studies. The efficiency of work would thus be maximised.*

117 *My services have taken due note of the work that you have already undertaken in this respect and*
118 *welcome the establishment of an ad hoc Working Group of experts including those from EFSA,*
119 *external experts and those from Member States to set clear review criteria for the scientific evidence*
120 *on BPA. Therefore, taking into account the timing for the activities involved in this work as foreseen*
121 *by EFSA, including a public consultation, as the first part of this mandate the Commission therefore*
122 *kindly requests EFSA:*

123 *- To establish a protocol detailing the criteria for new study inclusion and for toxicological*
124 *evidence appraisal for the re-evaluation of BPA as soon as possible, to ensure an efficient and*
125 *transparent re-assessment of BPA.*

126 *Once this work is complete, the Commission will kindly request EFSA the second part of this mandate:*

127 *- To re-evaluate the risks to public health related to the presence of BPA in foodstuffs, taking*
128 *into account the results of all relevant scientific data insofar as it meets the criteria laid down*
129 *in the protocol mentioned above and in line with the terms of reference set out in the annex*
130 *to this letter.*

131 *Whilst we consider it important to send this mandate now, the Commission views it as premature at*
132 *this stage to establish a deadline for the completion of the re-evaluation. Therefore, the Commission*
133 *is asking you to inform us on a feasible timeline for the second part of this mandate.*

134 *The present mandate does not include the re-evaluation of the exposure to BPA. At present the*
135 *Commission considers that there is no justification for such a re-evaluation. If this changes in the*
136 *future, the Commission will provide you with a specific mandate.*

137 **Terms of Reference**

138 *In accordance with Article 29(1)(a) of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002, the European Commission asks*
139 *EFSA to:*

140 *• establish a protocol detailing the criteria for new study inclusion and for toxicological*
141 *evidence appraisal for the re-evaluation of BPA, to ensure an efficient and transparent re-*
142 *assessment of BPA;*

143 *• re-evaluate the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs.*
144 *In particular, the re-evaluation should take into consideration new data available from the results*
145 *of the US NTP/ FDA study due in 2017 as well as all other new available information not*
146 *previously evaluated by EFSA and which fulfil the criteria laid down in an established protocol.*
147 *This re-evaluation should seek to clarify the remaining uncertainties concerning the toxicological*
148 *endpoints of BPA, especially those concerning the mammary gland, reproductive, metabolic,*

149 *neurobehavioural and immune systems and to establish a full tolerable daily intake (TDI) on the*
150 *basis of the new information available.”*

151 **1.3. Interpretation of the Terms of Reference**

152 To address both mandates, the protocol should define *a priori* the following processes inherent to BPA
153 hazard identification and characterisation:

- 154 • problem formulation (Section 2)
- 155 • gathering the evidence (Section 3)
- 156 • selecting the evidence (Section 4)
- 157 • collecting the data from the included studies (Section 5)
- 158 • appraising and weighing the evidence (Sections 6-8 and Appendices B-C)
- 159 • synthesis of the results (Appendix D)
- 160 • hazard characterisation (Section 10)
- 161 • uncertainty analysis (Section 11)

162 Protocol development is part of the on-going EFSA Prometheus project (EFSA, 2015) aimed at further
163 enhancing the methodological rigour, transparency and openness of EFSA scientific assessments. In
164 this context, the hazard assessment of BPA was chosen as a case-study to test the importance of
165 performing the assessment in two separate steps: 1) planning (protocol development) and 2)
166 implementation of the protocol.

167 **2. Problem formulation**

168 **2.1. Objectives of the hazard assessment**

169 The general aim of this hazard assessment is to assess whether the new scientific evidence (published
170 after 31/12/2012, and not previously appraised by the EFSA CEF Panel in 2015 and 2016) still
171 supports the current temporary TDI (t-TDI) for BPA of 4 µg/kg bw per day.

172 More specifically, the evaluation will cover:

- 173 (i) the adverse effects in humans associated with the exposure to BPA *via* any route;
- 174 (ii) the adverse effects in animals after oral exposure to BPA at doses below the cut-off of 10
175 mg/kg bw per day (based on the benchmark dose lower confidence interval (BMDL₁₀) in
176 mice used by the EFSA CEF Panel to set the t-TDI in 2015) or after subcutaneous exposure
177 to BPA doses below the cut-off of 0.5 mg/kg bw per day (based on the ratio of oral
178 bioavailability and of subcutaneous systemic availability in mice) or after dermal BPA
179 exposure at any dose;
- 180 (iii) the human and animal toxicokinetics of BPA.

181 The scientific evidence needed to directly address these objectives will be dealt with by applying a
182 narrative or a systematic approach as explained in details in the following sections.

183 The evaluation will deal with evidence available after the closing date of the literature search of the
184 previous EFSA BPA risk assessment (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015). The few studies published after
185 31/12/2012 and already appraised by the CEF Panel in its 2015 opinion or in its 2016 statement on
186 immunotoxicity (EFSA CEF Panel, 2016) will not be re-appraised. The conclusions from these two
187 previous EFSA assessments of BPA will be the starting point of the new assessment.

188 2.2. Target population

189 The target population of the hazard assessment is the EU general population, including specific
 190 vulnerable groups (unborn children and breast-fed infants).

191 2.3. Chemical of concern

192 The target chemical substance is bisphenol A (BPA; chemical formula C₁₅H₁₆O₂, CAS No 80-05-7 and
 193 EC No 201-245-8). BPA derivatives will not be object of the assessment.

194 2.4. Endpoints relevant to the hazard assessment

195 The potential adverse effects of BPA have been extensively characterised in previous risk assessments
 196 by EFSA (EFSA, 2006, 2008; EFSA CEF Panel, 2010, 2011, 2015) and international bodies such as
 197 WHO/FAO (2011) and US FDA (2013). Table 1 summarises the outcome of the Weight of Evidence
 198 (WoE) approach carried out in the 2015 EFSA comprehensive review on BPA (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015)
 199 and the degree of likelihood for the effects under consideration on the basis of the then available
 200 human and animal evidence.

201 **Table 1:** Likelihood² for BPA effects (as taken from outcome of WoE approach in EFSA CEF Panel,
 202 2015)

Effects classified as "Likely"
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General toxicity (liver and kidney weight increase) • Mammary gland proliferative changes
Effects classified "As likely as not"
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reproductive and developmental effects • Neurological, neurobehavioural and neuroendocrine effects • Immune effects • Cardiovascular effects • Metabolic effects • Carcinogenicity
Effects classified as "Unlikely"
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genotoxicity

203
 204 In the 2015 BPA risk assessment (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015), only the "Likely" effects of BPA (increase of
 205 liver and kidney weight and mammary gland proliferation) were brought forward for dose-response
 206 analysis and for defining the reference point for the health-based guidance value. The effects
 207 classified as "As likely as not" were considered in the uncertainty analysis and were taken into account
 208 in the definition of an extra factor for the derivation of the t-TDI.

209 The mean relative kidney weight increase in the two generation study in mice by Tyl *et al.* (2006,
 210 2008), for which a BMDL10 of 8.96 mg/kg bw per day was calculated, was used as the basis of a
 211 revised TDI (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015).

212 This dose in mice was extrapolated to an oral Human Equivalent Dose (HED) using the so called HED
 213 approach. This approach could be used in the 2015 EFSA CEF Panel opinion on BPA because of the
 214 availability for this chemical of (i) a solid base of toxicokinetic data in various laboratory animal
 215 species providing internal dose metrics for neonatal-to-adult stages and for different routes of
 216 exposure; (ii) physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models predicting internal exposures in
 217 laboratory animals and humans in a route-specific manner. In 2015, the HED value of 609 µg/kg bw
 218 per day was obtained by multiplying the mice BMDL10 by the Human Equivalent Dose Factor (HEDF)
 219 of 0.068 for oral exposure of adult mice. This HED was taken as the reference point for setting the
 220 new health-based guidance value for BPA. A t-TDI of 4 µg BPA/kg bw per day was obtained by
 221 dividing the HED by an overall uncertainty factor of 150 to account for intra-species differences (factor

² It is important to emphasise that the WoE approach referred specifically to hazard identification, i.e. it referred to the likelihood of an association between BPA exposure at any dose and the effect under consideration and not to the likelihood or frequency of the effect actually occurring in humans.

222 of 10), inter-species toxicodynamic differences (factor of 2.5) and uncertainties in the database
223 regarding mammary gland, reproductive, neurobehavioural, immune, and metabolic systems (extra
224 factor of 6). Notably, the default uncertainty factor of 4 for interspecies kinetic differences was already
225 accounted for by the use of the chemical-specific approach, in which the ratio of the Area Under the
226 Curve (AUC) in animals to the AUC in humans was used to adjust the external doses in animals to the
227 external doses in humans.

228 **2.5. Identification of the hazard assessment sub-questions**

229 This section illustrates the hazard assessment sub-questions to be answered and the review approach,
230 *i.e.* narrative *vs.* systematic³, to follow for the new BPA re-evaluation (Table 2).

231 In the hazard assessment a full systematic process will be followed to address human and animal
232 evidence of outcomes related to the exposure of BPA focussing on those effects considered “Likely”
233 and “As likely as not” in 2015 (Tables 1 and 2), with the intention to decrease the uncertainty
234 surrounding the conclusions.

235 Since the conclusions of the 2015 BPA opinion (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015) were underpinned by a
236 thorough review of toxicokinetic data in different animal species and PBPK models to derive an oral
237 HED, new evidence addressing BPA toxicokinetics in humans and animals will be reviewed - using a
238 narrative approach - to evaluate whether the previously used HEDF should be changed. The definition
239 of the various HEDF to be used for dose extrapolation from animal to human according to species,
240 exposure time and route will be determined at the WoE step to ensure comparability of the effects
241 across different studies and species.

242 Since the evidence from the EFSA CEF Panel 2015 opinion was not conclusive with regards to the
243 mode of action of BPA, new studies that could potentially help elucidating this aspect will be part of
244 the review and will be dealt with narratively.

245 Additional sub-questions will refer to the assessment of the dose-response relationship and an
246 evaluation of possible uncertainties, for example those derived from consideration of the toxicokinetic
247 and toxicodynamic properties of BPA and from considerations of inter-species variability in case animal
248 data are being used for deriving a health-based guidance value.

249

³For a comparison between a systematic and a narrative review, the reader should refer to Table 2 of the Guidance of EFSA (2010): Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. EFSA Journal 2010; 8(6):1637. [90 pp.]. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1637. Available online: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1637/epdf>

250 **Table 2:** Hazard assessment sub-questions

Q#	Hazard assessment step	Hazard assessment sub-questions	Approach
1	Hazard Identification	Is there new evidence with regards to any association between exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and general toxicity (<i>e.g.</i> liver and kidney), or reproductive and developmental, neurological, immune, cardiovascular, metabolic, mammary gland or carcinogenic outcomes in <u>humans</u> ?	Systematic
2	Hazard Identification	Is there new evidence with regards to any association between oral (below 10 mg BPA/kg bw per day), subcutaneous (below 0.5 mg/kg bw per day) or dermal exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and general toxicity (<i>e.g.</i> liver and kidney) or reproductive/developmental, neurological, immune, cardiovascular, metabolic mammary gland or carcinogenic outcomes in <u>mammalian animals</u> ?	Systematic
3	Hazard Identification	Is there new evidence with regards to BPA genotoxicity <i>in vitro</i> or <i>in vivo</i> ?	Narrative
4	Hazard Identification	Is there new evidence with regards to an association between exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and any outcome not mentioned in Q1 in <u>humans</u> ?	Systematic
5	Hazard Identification	Is there new evidence with regards to an association between exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and any outcome not mentioned in Q2 in <u>mammalian animals</u> ?	Systematic
6	Hazard Identification	What is the new evidence with regards to the mode of action (MoA) of BPA arising from <i>in vitro</i> studies at concentrations lower than 100 nM ⁴ ?	Narrative
7	Hazard Identification	Is there new evidence with regards to the MoA of BPA arising from other MoA studies?	Narrative
8	Hazard characterisation	Is there new evidence with regards to BPA toxicokinetics in humans?	Narrative
9	Hazard characterisation	Is there new evidence with regards to BPA toxicokinetics in experimental <u>mammalian</u> animal species/strains?	Narrative
10	Hazard characterisation	Does the new evidence on the toxicokinetics of BPA in humans and experimental <u>mammalian</u> animals still support the same HED factors used in the 2015 EFSA opinion on BPA?	Informed by sub-questions 8 & 9
11	Hazard characterisation	What is the dose-response relationship for relevant outcomes in humans?	Informed by sub-questions 1 & 4
12	Hazard characterisation	What is the dose-response relationship for relevant outcomes in experimental animals according to the new evidence?	Informed by sub-questions 2, 3 & 5

251

252 **3. Methods for gathering the evidence**253 **3.1. Time span of evidence search**

254 The evaluation will deal with new evidence available since 1 January 2013. The studies published in
 255 2013 and already appraised by EFSA in its 2015 opinion on BPA or in its 2016 statement on
 256 immunotoxicity of BPA (EFSA CEF Panel, 2015 and 2016) will not be re-assessed in the re-evaluation.

⁴ See rationale for choice of this cut-off concentration in Section 4.2.4.3

257 The proposed ending date is 31/12/2017 unless the publication of the NTP/FDA study is delayed.

258 **3.2. Information sources**

259 Literature searches will be conducted in the following bibliographic databases (see Appendix A):

- 260 • PubMed
- 261 • Web of Science™ Core Collection
- 262 • Scopus
- 263 • Toxline + DART (TOXNET platform)

264 Furthermore, EFSA will carry out a call for data in order to gather study reports and other information.

265 An open search strategy will be used, including only the terms “BPA” or “Bisphenol A” and synonyms
266 with a view to capture as many records as possible.

267 The search strings proposed to be used for each database search are annexed in Appendix A and will
268 be published in their final form in the BPA scientific opinion, to ensure transparency and reproducibility
269 of the results.

270 **3.3. Type of evidence**

271 Only primary research studies will be considered for the assessment.

272 Reviews will only be used to check whether they contain additional references of primary studies that
273 have not been captured by the literature search/call for data.

274 Comments, letters to the editors, book chapters, poster and/or conference abstracts will be excluded.

275 **3.4. Management of the information**

276 The evidence retrieved from each bibliographic database or obtained through the call for data will be
277 imported in the bibliographic reference management software EndNote and combined together. A first
278 removal of duplicates will be done at this step using the functionality available in the EndNote
279 reference manager software.

280 The EndNote file obtained from the merge of the records retrieved from the different sources of
281 information will be uploaded into an online systematic review tool, DistillerSR⁵, for the subsequent
282 steps of the review.

283 Following uploading of the records into DistillerSR, removal of duplicates will again be undertaken,
284 using the Duplicate Detection feature of the tool.

285 **4. Methods for selecting the studies**

286 **4.1. Screening of titles and abstracts**

287 The titles, and where available, the abstracts identified in the searches described in Section 3 and
288 Appendix A will be screened for relevance to the general scope of the assessment: is the paper
289 relevant to (i) exposure to humans OR (ii) exposure to animals OR (iii) mode of action.

290 The screening of titles and abstract will be performed by two independent reviewers.

291 The Distiller SR tool will allow for the identification of potential disagreements between the two
292 reviewers on study eligibility.

293 In case of disagreement between the two independent reviewers, the paper will be automatically
294 brought to the next screening phase, *i.e.* at the level of full text.

⁵ DistillerSR - <https://www.evidencepartners.com/products/distillersr-systematic-review-software/>

295 4.2. Examining full-text reports for eligibility of studies

296 For records that pass the first screening based on titles and abstracts, the full text will undergo a
297 second screening against the inclusion criteria by means of two independent reviewers.

298 This step will also serve for the first categorisation of the studies into the different health outcome
299 categories identified in the sub-questions in Table 2.

300 The possibility of an “unclear” reply is no longer foreseen at this stage because all the information
301 needed for taking a decision will be available in the full text.

302 In case of disagreement, the two independent reviewers will discuss the paper in order to find a
303 solution to solve it. In case an agreement between the two reviewers cannot be found the paper will
304 be brought to the attention of the Working Group (WG) on BPA assessment for the final decision.

305 Study reports and other information made available through the call for data to EFSA will also follow
306 this procedure.

307 4.2.1. Availability of full-text and language

308 Availability of the full text in English will be a pre-requisite for an article to be included in the
309 assessment. Furthermore, authors of publications other than in English will have the opportunity to
310 submit their full text articles translated in English for consideration by EFSA through the call for data.
311 Such translated studies will undergo the same appraisal process as the other literature as far as they
312 meet *all* the other applied inclusion criteria.

313 The reviewers will thus be asked to reply to these questions:

- 314 • Is the full text available?
- 315 • Is the full text in English?

316 If the answer to one of these two questions is “No”, the record will be excluded from the assessment.
317 If the answer to both questions is “Yes”, the reviewers will be prompted to reply to the next question.

318 The decision of excluding publications in languages other than English may be a source of uncertainty,
319 but it is based on the available EFSA resources

320 4.2.2. Type of studies

321 The reviewers will be asked to reply to the following question:

- 322 • Is the paper a primary or a secondary study?

323 If the answer to the question is “primary”, the reviewers will be prompted to reply to the following
324 question.

325 If the answer to the question is “secondary”, the record will be excluded from the assessment but it
326 will be used to check whether it contains additional references of primary studies that have not been
327 captured by the literature search/call for data.

328 If the answer to the question is “other”, the record will be excluded from the assessment.

329 4.2.3. Outcomes of interest

330 In the first instance the reviewers will be asked to confirm that the record relates to a study reporting
331 information considered relevant to the review question *i.e.* on BPA exposure in humans or in animals
332 or on the mode of action of BPA (*e.g. in vitro*, cell cultures, specific molecular pathways). Primary
333 studies that are not aimed at studying effects associated with exposure to BPA (*e.g.* human
334 biomonitoring studies) will be excluded at this step.

335 If the answer to the question is “Yes”, the reviewers will be prompted to reply to the following
336 question.

337 If the answer to the question is “No”, the record will be excluded from the assessment.

338 The reviewers will then classify the studies considered relevant for the assessment as providing
339 information on:

- 340 • Effects associated with human exposure to BPA
- 341 • Effects associated with animal exposure to BPA
- 342 • Mode of action (*in vitro*, non-mammalian animals, microbiota, *etc.*)

343

344 The effects considered relevant for the assessment will be classified in the following health outcome
345 categories: general toxicity (*e.g.* liver and kidney), reproductive, developmental, neurological,
346 immune, cardiovascular, metabolic, mammary gland or carcinogenic, genotoxic or any other effects
347 with the addition of toxicokinetic studies.

348 One source may report on more than one outcome of interest and each outcome will be assessed
349 separately.

350 **4.2.4. Exposure of interest**

351 **4.2.4.1. Human studies**

352 For human studies, all types of exposure to BPA (alone or in mixtures) will be considered, including
353 occupational exposure scenario.

354 **4.2.4.2. Animal studies**

355 For animal studies to be considered for the assessment, exposure to BPA (not given as a part of a
356 mixture) via the oral, subcutaneous or dermal routes will be investigated.

357 For oral studies, at least one of the doses tested must be below the oral cut-off value of 10 mg
358 BPA/kg bw per day (based on the BMDL10 of 8.96 mg/kg bw per day used for the EFSA t-TDI in
359 2015) given that the main focus of the new BPA hazard assessment will be on low dose effects.

360 For subcutaneous studies a cut-off of 0.5 mg/kg bw per day (based on the ratio of oral bioavailability
361 and of subcutaneous systemic availability in mice) for at least one of the tested subcutaneous doses
362 will be applied.

363 For dermal studies, no cut-off values will be set for study inclusion because of the unavailability of the
364 necessary toxicokinetic data for the calculation of the route-specific conversion factor.

365 Studies via the inhalation route will not be included as this is not considered as a relevant route of
366 BPA exposure for consumers.

367 **4.2.4.3. Mode of action studies**

368 Studies that investigate possible mode of action of BPA must be conducted using BPA alone at
369 concentrations that are considered to be in a toxicologically relevant range; hence *in vitro* studies will
370 be considered only if at least one of the concentrations tested is below 100 nM. In defining this cut-off
371 concentration, we have considered the concentration of unconjugated BPA in humans, as published by
372 Thayer *et al.* (2015), at the exposure levels identified in the 2015 EFSA CEF Panel opinion. In addition
373 a factor of 10 has been applied to account for the amount possibly being absorbed by the
374 experimental devices.

375 For *in vitro* genotoxicity studies, this cut-off value will not be applied to ensure that this MoA can
376 become manifest.

377 Concerning non mammal animal models (*e.g.* zebrafish) or other *in vivo* studies, no cut-off doses will
378 be applied, hence studies will be included for mode of action analysis, if applicable.

379

4.2.5. Inclusion/exclusion criteria for human, animal and MoA studies

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381
382 Tables 3, 4 and 5 schematically list the criteria for including or excluding from the review human,
383 animal and MoA studies, respectively.

384 Only epidemiological studies with cohort and case-control designs will be systematically appraised for
385 humans. Studies with a cross-sectional design bear some limitations in relation to the scope of the
386 BPA review and therefore will only be considered in case of need for supporting information in a
387 narrative manner.

388 Studies reporting either levels of unconjugated or conjugated BPA will be considered relevant, taking
389 into consideration the limit of detection for the unconjugated BPA and the existing exposures.

390 Studies in which levels of BPA have been measured in human biological samples only once will not be
391 included as exposure assessment is uncertain, with the exception of studies in pregnant women,
392 which could be relevant for time-windows of exposure.

393 **Table 3:** Inclusion/exclusion criteria related to human studies

<u>Sub-question 1:</u> Is there an association between exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and general toxicity (<i>e.g.</i> liver and kidney), or reproductive and developmental, neurological, immune, cardiovascular, metabolic, mammary gland or carcinogenic outcomes in <u>humans</u> ?		
<u>Sub-question 3:</u> Is there new evidence with regards to BPA genotoxicity <i>in vitro</i> or <i>in vivo</i> ? (narrative approach)?		
<u>Sub-question 4:</u> Is there an association between exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and any outcome not mentioned in Q1 in humans?		
<u>Sub-question 8:</u> Is there new evidence with regards to BPA toxicokinetics in humans (narrative approach)?		
<u>Sub-question 11:</u> What is the BPA dose-response relationship for relevant outcomes in humans?		
Study design	In	Cohort studies Case-control studies (retrospective and nested) Toxicokinetic studies on any route of exposure (narrative approach)
	Out	Cross sectional studies Animal studies <i>In vitro</i> studies
Population	In	All populations groups, all ages, males and females
	Out	/
Exposure/ intervention	In	All routes of exposure All studies during pregnancy including those with single spot urine samples Studies in which levels of BPA have been measured in human biological samples more than once
	Out	Biomonitoring studies Studies with single spot urine samples in non-pregnant individuals
Language	In	English
	Out	Other languages
Time	In	From 01/01/2013 (except those which were already included in the 2015 opinion)
	Out	Before 2013
Publication type	In	Primary research studies (<i>i.e.</i> studies generating new data)
	Out	Secondary studies* Expert opinions, editorials, and letters to the editor PhD Theses Extended abstracts, conference proceedings

394 * they will be used to obtain additional references of primary research studies

395

396

397 **Table 4:** Inclusion/exclusion criteria related to experimental mammalian animal studies

Sub-question 2: Is there new evidence with regards to any association between oral (below 10 mg BPA/kg bw per day), subcutaneous (below 0.5 mg/kg bw per day) or dermal exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and general toxicity (*e.g.* liver and kidney) or reproductive/developmental, neurological, immune, cardiovascular, metabolic mammary gland or carcinogenic outcomes in mammalian animals?

Sub-question 3: Is there new evidence with regards to BPA genotoxicity *in vivo* at any dose (narrative approach)?

Sub-question 5: Is there an association between exposure to BPA at any pre- and/or postnatal life stage and any outcome not mentioned in Q2 in mammalian animals?

Sub-question 9: Is there new evidence with regards to BPA toxicokinetics in experimental mammalian animal species/strains (narrative approach)?

Sub-question 12: What is the dose-response relationship for relevant outcomes in experimental animals according to the new evidence??

Study design	In	<i>In vivo</i> studies on animals not examining MoA Toxicokinetic studies (narrative approach)
	Out	Human studies <i>In vitro</i> studies
Population	In	All mammalian animals
	Out	Non-mammalian animals
Exposure/ intervention	In	Oral, sub-cutaneous and dermal. Studies in which levels of BPA have been measured in biological samples At least one tested dose below the cut-off of 10 mg/kg bw per day for oral studies or 0.5 mg/kg bw per day for subcutaneous studies (no cut-off is applied to dermal studies) All <i>in vivo</i> genotoxicity studies with no cut-off dose
	Out	Exposure routes other than oral, dermal, or subcutaneous Mixtures
Language	In	English
	Out	Other languages
Time	In	From 01/01/2013 (except those already included in the 2015 opinion and the 2016 statement on BPA immunotoxicity)
	Out	Before 2013
Publication type	In	Primary research studies (<i>i.e.</i> studies generating new data)
	Out	Secondary studies* Expert opinions, editorials, and letters to the editor PhD Theses Extended abstracts, conference proceedings

* they will be used to obtain additional references of primary research studies

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401 **Table 5:** Inclusion/exclusion criteria related to MoA studies

Sub-question 3: Is there new evidence with regards to BPA genotoxicity *in vitro* at any concentration (narrative approach)?

Sub-question 6: What is the evidence of the MoA of BPA arising from *in vitro* studies at concentrations lower than 100 nM (narrative approach)?

Sub-question 7: What is the evidence of the MoA of BPA arising from other studies (narrative approach)?

Study design	In	<i>In vitro</i> studies <i>In vivo</i> studies on MoA in humans, mammalian and non-mammalian animals
	Out	Human studies or <i>in vivo</i> studies not examining MoA
Exposure/ intervention	In	At least one concentration below the cut-off of 100 nM for <i>in vitro</i> studies (except for <i>in vitro</i> genotoxicity studies) All <i>in vitro</i> genotoxicity studies All routes of exposure for <i>in vivo</i> studies
	Out	Mixtures <i>In vitro</i> studies (except for <i>in vitro</i> genotoxicity studies) testing BPA only above 100 nM
Language	In	English
	Out	Other languages
Time	In	From 01/01/2013 (except those already included in the 2015 opinion)
	Out	Before 2013
Publication type	In	Primary research studies (<i>i.e.</i> studies generating new data)
	Out	Expert opinions, editorials, and letters to the editor PhD Theses Extended abstracts, conference proceedings Secondary studies

402 **5. Methods for collecting the data from the included studies**403 **5.1. Data extraction**

404 Pre-defined data extraction forms (see Tables 6-7) will be used for collecting the data from the
 405 individual studies undergoing a systematic review approach and an internal validity appraisal. These
 406 extraction forms will be implemented using Distillers SR, the same software used in the previously
 407 described steps.

408

409 **Table 6:** Data extraction from human studies

Study ID	Reference:
	Study name and acronym (if applicable):
	Total number of subjects:
	Health outcome category ^(a) :
Funding	Funding source(s):
Study design	Cohort study Case control study
	Type of blinding:
	Year the study was conducted (start):
	Duration/length of follow-up:
	Dates of sampling (when relevant):
	Dates of analysis of BPA/BPA-conjugates in the samples:
Subjects	Number of participants in the study: Participation rates (%):
	Number of exposed/non exposed subjects : Follow-up rates by group (%):
	Sex (male/female):
	Geography (country, region, state, <i>etc.</i>):
	Age at exposure
	Race and ethnicity
	Socioeconomic background
	Confounders and other variables ^(b) as reported
	Outcome assessment (<i>e.g.</i> mean, median, measures of variance as presented in paper such as SD, SEM, 75th/90th/95th percentile, minimum/maximum):
	Inclusion and exclusion criteria:
Intervention/exposure	Exposure: - Measured levels in human biological samples (<i>e.g.</i> breast milk, blood, urine) and method used (Validation of the method, measures to avoid contamination of samples, <i>etc.</i>) - Estimated dietary exposure and method used (Validation of the method, measures to avoid contamination of samples, <i>etc.</i>)
Methods for endpoint assessment	Parameters measured (units of measure, measures of central tendency and dispersion, CI level)
	Diagnostic or method to measure health outcome (including self-reporting):
Statistical analysis	Statistical method used
Results	Measures of effect and corresponding confidence interval at each exposure level as reported in the paper, and for each sub-group when applicable: Were sub-groups analyses predefined (yes/no, if not, how was it justified)? How were the variables treated (continuous or transformed or categorical)?
	Statistical test used: Modifying factors: other potential sources of bias considered in the analysis, and how they were considered:
	Shape of dose-response if reported by the authors (<i>e.g.</i> description of whether shape appears to be monotonic, non-monotonic, according to the study authors):

410 (a): General toxicity (*e.g.* liver and kidney), reproductive, developmental, neurological, immune, cardiovascular, metabolic (*e.g.*
 411 diabetes, thyroid function, obesity), mammary gland or carcinogenic, genotoxic, other (more than one option should be
 412 possible).

413 (b): Age, sex, race/ethnicity, education/sociodemographic characteristics, smoking status, BMI, dietary factors, alcohol
 414 consumption, concurrent exposures (other chemicals/drugs)

415

416 **Table 7:** Data extraction from animal studies

Study ID	Reference:
	Year the study was conducted (start, if available):
	Health outcome category ^(a)
Funding	Funding source(s):
Type of study and guideline	Type of study ^(b) :
	GLP (yes/no): Guidelines studies (if yes specify):
Animal model	Species/(sub-)strain/line:
	Disease models (<i>e.g.</i> infection, diabetes, allergy, obesity, autoimmune disease):
Housing conditions and diet	Housing conditions (including cages, bottles, bedding)
	Diet name and source:
	Background levels of phytoestrogens in the diet (type and levels):
Exposure	BPA provider
	Compound purity (if available, specify impurities identified):
	Vehicle used: Dose regimen (dose level or concentration of BPA per group, and frequency):
	Route of administration (diet, gavage, subcutaneous):
	Period of exposure (pre-mating, mating, gestation, lactation, adult)
Study design	Duration of the exposure:
	Sex and age of the initially exposed animals:
	Number of groups/ number of animals per group:
	Randomisation procedures at start of the study:
	Reducing (culling) of litters and method:
	Number of pups per litter for next generation and methodology:
	Number of pups per litter/animals for certain measurements and methodology:
	Time of measurement/Observation period (pre-mating, mating, gestation, lactation, adult):
Endpoints measured:	
Statistical analysis	Methods to measure endpoint:
	Statistical method used:
Results:	Concentration of the test compound in vehicle (analysed, stated, unclear):
	Documentation of details for dose conversion when conducted:
	Level of test compound(s) in tissue or blood:
	Results per dose or concentration (<i>e.g.</i> mean, median, frequency, measures of precision or variance):
	NOEL, NOAEL, LOEL, LOAEL, BMD/BMDL, and statistical significance of other dose levels (author's interpretation):
	Shape of dose response if reported by the authors (<i>e.g.</i> description of whether shape appears to be monotonic, non-monotonic, NA for single exposure or treatment group studies)

417 (a): General toxicity (*e.g.* liver and kidney), reproductive, developmental, neurological, immune, cardiovascular, metabolic (*e.g.*
 418 diabetes, thyroid function, obesity), mammary gland or carcinogenic, genotoxic, other (more than one option possible).

419 (b): *e.g.* acute, sub-acute (*i.e.* 4 weeks), subchronic (*i.e.* 13 weeks), chronic (*i.e.* 104 weeks), multigenerational,
 420 developmental, carcinogenicity.

421

422 6. Relevance of studies to the hazard sub-questions

423 After data extraction and study classification according to the health outcome category, each study
 424 will undergo the assessment of its relevance. For the sake of clarity, the reader should note that
 425 relevance will be assessed in two stages:

426 (i) Relevance of the studies to the sub-question (for both human and animal studies): as a first
427 stage, the relevance will be evaluated for every endpoint in each individual study in relation
428 to the specific hazard sub-question asked (see Table 2).

429 (ii) Relevance of effects for human health (for animal studies only): this assessment will take
430 place after the WoE evaluation and will not be done for individual studies. It will be done for
431 the effects identified in animals through the WoE analysis, for which an evaluation of the
432 relevance to human health will be made by expert judgement (see Section 8).

433 The outcome of the evaluation of the relevance of the endpoint to the sub-question could be "yes
434 (Y)", "unclear (U)" or "no (N)". Endpoints rated as having no relevance for any health outcome
435 category will not be carried forward for internal validity appraisal. The judgement for individual study
436 relevance will be included in the WoE table.

437 Each evaluation will be performed by two independent reviewers. In case of disagreement the
438 reviewers will first discuss to try to find an agreement, and if this is not possible, the paper will be
439 brought to the attention of the working group and EFSA staff who will take the final decision. The
440 process will have to be fully documented, making sure a justification for the judgement is provided.

441 **7. Internal validity of the studies**

442 An overview of the whole process is provided schematically in Fig. 1.

443 For every endpoint in each study, two components of internal validity will be rated: (i) quality and (ii)
444 risk of bias (RoB). The definition of what is meant by each term in the context of the present
445 assessment is reported below.

446 Quality: Intrinsic ability of the methodology and experimental design of a study to provide accurate
447 evidence with regards to the endpoint/effect under investigation.

448 Risk of bias (RoB): The systematic error caused by systematic differences (including environmental
449 conditions or data handling, exposure, study design (blinding) between the control and experimental
450 subjects (other than the (intervention or) exposure of interest).

451 Each evaluation will be performed by two independent reviewers. In case of disagreements between
452 the reviewers, they will discuss in order to find an agreement. If an agreement cannot be found, the
453 paper will be brought to the attention of the working group and EFSA staff who will take the final
454 decision. The appraisal will be conducted separately for each study by the outcome of interest
455 reported. The evaluation of all studies will only be based on the reported information/data. Due to
456 limited resources the study authors will not be contacted for clarifications or missing information.

457 The process (see flowchart below) will start with the evaluation of the study quality, at the end of
458 which the study will be rated as either "Reliable without restrictions", "Reliable with restrictions" or
459 "Not reliable". If the rating is "Not reliable", the study will not undergo any further assessment and
460 this will be recorded.

461 For animal studies the appraisal of quality will be performed using criteria that were adapted from
462 SciRAP (Beronius *et al.*, 2014, revised version at www.scirap.org, see Appendix B3). For human
463 studies, since the criteria from SciRAP are not applicable, the assessment of quality will be performed
464 using criteria that were adapted from the NTP Risk of Bias tool (NTP OHAT, 2015, see Appendices B1
465 and B2).

466 The quality assessment will be followed by the RoB evaluation using an adapted protocol from NTP
467 developed separately for human and animal studies (NTP OHAT, 2015, see Appendix C). The appraisal
468 of RoB will be performed only for those studies which have been rated for quality as "Reliable with or
469 without restrictions". At the end of the RoB evaluation, the studies will be rated as "High RoB",
470 "Medium RoB", or "Low RoB".

471 After an overall evaluation of the quality and RoB aspects has been made, the two distinct ratings will
472 be combined to obtain three tiers of internal validity, from 1 to 3 corresponding to decreasing levels of
473 internal validity. All the studies belonging to tiers 1-3 will be considered in the WoE analysis with
474 different impacts on the conclusions drawn by expert judgement on the likelihood of an effect.

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Step 4: setting tiers of internal validity

		Quality rating	
		Reliable without restrictions	Reliable with restrictions
Risk of Bias rating	Low RoB	Tier 1	Tier 2
	Medium RoB	Tier 2	Tier 3
	High RoB	Tier 3	Not further considered

497

498 **Figure 1:** Individual study appraisal summary scheme done separately for each endpoint

499

500 7.1. Quality appraisal of human studies

501 The appraisal tool developed for the assessment of the quality of human studies is presented in Table
 502 8. The evaluation of quality will be performed focussing on four questions that EFSA experts have
 503 extrapolated and adapted from the NTP OHAT Risk of Bias rating tool for human studies (NTP OHAT,
 504 2015). Three out of four questions are considered as key (A-C) with regards to the overall quality
 505 assessment. The question on statistics was deemed as non-key due to the difficulties in explicitly
 506 formalising the criteria for an appropriate statistical method. In line with the NTP methodology, each
 507 question can have four possible answers ranging from "Definitely appropriate (++)" or "Probably
 508 appropriate (+)" to "Probably not appropriate (-)" or "Definitely not appropriate (--)".

509 The instructions on how to rate each quality aspect can be found in Appendices B1 and B2.

510 **Table 8:** Quality appraisal tool for human studies (case-control and cohort study design)

#	Key Q	Question	Domain	Rating (++, +, -, --)
1	A	Can we be confident in the exposure characterisation (methods)?	Detection	
2	B	Can we be confident in the outcome assessment (methods)?	Detection	
3	C	Was the time-window between exposure and outcome assessment appropriate?	Exposure	
4		Do the statistical methods seem appropriate?	Other	
Overall assessment of quality				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliable without restrictions (R) • Reliable with restrictions (RR)

511

512 The ratings of the quality key and non-key questions (++, +, -, --) will be integrated to obtain an
 513 overall study quality rating (*i.e.* "Reliable without restrictions", "Reliable with restrictions", "Not
 514 reliable"), as indicated below. This scheme will be tested in a pilot phase during the public consultation
 515 and might be modified according to the results and public consultation outcome.

516 **Reliable without restrictions:**

- 517 • At least two key questions (1-3) are scored with ++ and no key question is scored with - / - -
- 518 **AND**
- 519 • the non-key question 4 is scored with + / ++

520

521 **Reliable with restrictions:**

- 522 • All the other combinations not falling under either "Reliable without restrictions" or "Not
 523 reliable"

524

525 **Not reliable:**

- 526
- At least one key question (1-3) is scored with - / --

527 **OR**

- 528
- the non-key question 4 is scored with –

529

530 If the study quality rating is “Not reliable”, the study will not undergo the RoB evaluation and will be
531 excluded from the assessment. This will be recorded.

532 Only the studies that will be rated as “Reliable (with or without restrictions)” will be evaluated for RoB.

533 **7.2. Risk of bias appraisal for human studies**534 The questions that will address the RoB of human studies are presented in Table 9. Two out six
535 questions are considered key. Each individual element will be rated (“Definitely low RoB (++)”,
536 “Probably low RoB (+)”, “Probably high RoB (-)”, “Definitely high RoB (--”). Whenever one of the
537 elements to be appraised for RoB is not reported, this will be by default judged as “Probably high
538 RoB”. However, when there is indirect evidence that the element to be appraised was implemented in
539 the correct way or would have not appreciably affected the results, a categorisation of “Probably low
540 RoB” should be given.

541 The instructions on how to rate each RoB aspect can be found in Appendices C1 and C2.

542 **Table 9:** Risk of bias appraisal tool for human studies (case-control and cohort study design)

#	Key Q	Question	Domain	Rating (++, +, -, --)
1	A	Did selection of study participants result in appropriate comparison groups?	Selection	
2	B	Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables?	Confounding	
3		Were outcome data completely reported without attrition or exclusion of experimental units from analysis?	Attrition	
4		Was the exposure characterised consistently across study groups?	Detection	
5		Was the outcome assessment adequately blinded and consistent across study groups?	Detection	
6		Were all measured outcomes reported?	Selective reporting	
Overall rating				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low RoB • Medium RoB • High RoB

543

544 The ratings of the RoB key and non-key questions (++, +, -, --) will be integrated to obtain an overall
545 study RoB rating (“Low RoB”, “Medium RoB”, or “High RoB”) as follows.

546

547 **Low RoB:**

- 548 • All the key questions (1, 2) are scored with +/++
549 **AND**
550 • No more than two non-key questions (≤ 2) (3, 4, 5, 6) are scored with -
551 **AND**
552 • No non-key question is scored with --

553
554 **Medium RoB:**

555 All the other combinations not included either in “Low RoB” or in “High RoB”

556
557 **High RoB:**

- 558 • One key question is scored with -/--
559 **OR**
560 • Any non-key question is scored with --

561

562 **7.3. Quality appraisal of animal studies**

563 The appraisal tool developed for the assessment of the quality of animal studies is presented in Table
564 10. The quality criteria which have been taken from the SciRAP tool have been adapted by the experts
565 for the purpose of BPA safety assessment.

566 Six aspects were considered as having a higher relative weight and were identified as key (A-F) when
567 determining the overall quality rating.

568 Each quality aspect will be evaluated as “Fulfilled” (F), “Partially Fulfilled” (PF) or “Not Fulfilled” (NF).

569 The instruction on how to obtain these ratings can be found in Appendix B3.

570

571 **Table 10:** Quality appraisal tool (adapted from SciRAP)

#	Key Q	Quality aspect	Rating [Fulfilled (F), Partially Fulfilled (PF) Not fulfilled (NF)]
1		The test compound or mixture was unlikely to contain any impurities that may significantly have affected its toxicity.	
2	A	A concurrent negative control group was included.	
3	B	A reliable and sensitive animal model was used for investigating the test compound and selected endpoints.	
4		Animals were individually identified.	
5		Housing conditions (temperature, relative humidity, light-dark cycle) were appropriate for the study type and animal model.	
6		The number of animals per sex in each cage was appropriate for the study type and animal model.	
7		The test system is unlikely to contain contaminants that could affect study results, such as phytoestrogens and estrogenic contamination.	
8		An adequate number of doses was selected	
9	C	The timing and duration of administration do not seem to be inappropriate for investigating the included endpoints.	
10	D	Reliable and sensitive test methods were used for investigating the selected endpoints.	
11	E	Measurements do not seem to have been collected at unsuitable time point in order to generate sensitive, valid and reliable data.	
12	F	The statistical methods have been clearly described and do not seem inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar and a sufficient number of animals per dose group was used	
Overall assessment of quality			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliable without restrictions (R) • Reliable with restrictions (RR) • Not reliable (NR)

572

573 The following criteria were set in order to rate the study quality as either "Reliable without
574 restrictions", "Reliable with restrictions" or "Not reliable".

575 **Reliable without restrictions:**

- 576 • All the key questions (2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 12) are FULFILLED
577 **AND**
578 • All the non-key questions (1,4,5,6, 7, 8) are at least PARTIALLY fulfilled
579

580 **Reliable with restrictions:**

581 All the other combinations not falling under either "Reliable without restrictions" or "Not Reliable"

582 **Not reliable:**

- 583 • One of the key questions (2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 12) is NOT fulfilled
584 **OR**
585 • All the key questions (2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 12) are at least PARTIALLY fulfilled
586 **AND**
587 • More than 3 non-key questions (1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8) are NOT fulfilled.
588

589 As was the case for the appraisal of human studies, if the study quality is rated as “Not reliable” the
 590 study will not be evaluated for RoB and will be excluded from the assessment.

591 7.4. Risk of bias appraisal for animal studies

592 The questions that will address the RoB of animal studies are presented in Table 11. Each individual
 593 element will be rated (“Definitely low RoB (++)”, “Probably low RoB (+)”, “Probably high RoB (-)”,
 594 “Definitely high RoB (--)”).

595 The instructions on how to rate each RoB aspect can be found in Appendix C3.

596 **Table 11:** Risk of bias tool for animal studies

#	Key Q	Question	Domain	Rating (++, +, -, --)
1	A	Was administered dose or exposure level adequately randomised?	Selection	
2		Was allocation to study group adequately concealed	Selection	
3		Were experimental conditions identical across study groups?	Performance	
4	B	Were outcome data completely reported without attrition or exclusion from analysis?	Attrition	
5		Can we be confident in the exposure characterisation?	Detection	
6	C	Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?	Detection	
7		Were all measured outcomes reported?	Selective Reporting	
Overall rating				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low RoB • Medium RoB • High RoB

597

598 As a last step, the scores for the different questions will be integrated to obtain the study overall RoB
 599 estimate (“High RoB”, “Medium RoB” or “Low RoB”).

600 Three key questions, with higher relative weight when determining the overall RoB rating, were
 601 selected. The rules to follow to obtain the integrated RoB rating are shown below.

602 **Low RoB:**

- 603 • All the key questions are scored with + /++

604 **AND**

- 605 • None of the non-key questions are scored with - - and no more than two with -.

606

607 **Medium RoB:**

- 608 • All the other combinations not falling under either “High RoB” or “Low RoB”.

609

610 **High RoB:**

- 611 • Any key question is scored with a - /--

612 **OR**

- 613 • More than two non-key questions are scored with a - / --.

614 7.5. Conclusion on internal validity of human and animal studies

615 After an overall evaluation of the quality and RoB aspects has been made, the two distinct ratings will
 616 be combined to obtain three tiers of internal validity, from 1 to 3 corresponding to decreasing levels of
 617 internal validity, as shown in Table 12.

618 Please note when the quality appraisal of a study is rated as "Not reliable", the study will not undergo
 619 the RoB evaluation and will then be excluded from the assessment ("Not further considered" in the
 620 matrix below). Similarly, studies rated as "Reliable with restrictions" with "High RoB" will be excluded
 621 from any further assessment. Only studies considered as "Reliable without restrictions" and with "Low
 622 RoB" will be allocated to Tier 1. Those "Reliable without restrictions" will be allocated to either Tiers 2
 623 or 3 depending on the rating of the RoB as "Medium" or "Low", respectively. The studies "Reliable
 624 with restrictions" will be classified in Tier 2 if the RoB is rated as "Low" or Tier 3 if RoB is rated as
 625 "Medium".

626 **Table 12:** Internal validity

		Quality rating		
		Reliable without restrictions	Reliable with restrictions	Not reliable
Risk of Bias rating	Low RoB	Tier 1	Tier 2	Not further considered
	Medium RoB	Tier 2	Tier 3	Not further considered
	High RoB	Tier 3	Not further considered	Not further considered

627

628 8. Weight of evidence approach

629 Following the appraisal of the individual human and animal studies for internal validity and relevance
 630 to the questions, the experts will evaluate the confidence in the overall body of evidence by applying a
 631 WoE approach supported by a graphical representation of the study features, results and appraisal.
 632 This analysis will be performed in accordance with the draft guidance on the use of the WoE approach
 633 in scientific assessments by the EFSA Scientific Committee (2017). The WoE evaluation will allow an
 634 estimation of the overall likelihood that BPA is hazardous with respect to certain toxicological
 635 endpoints in human/animal studies, considering the findings for all of the exposure levels examined.

636 In order to be able to combine the whole body of evidence from animal studies into a single figure,
 637 potential differences in internal exposure have to be considered due to interspecies toxicokinetic
 638 differences. To deal with such differences, the HED concept has been used in the previous EFSA CEF
 639 Panel opinion on BPA (2015), as explained in Section 2.4 of this protocol. To apply this concept in the
 640 re-evaluation, data on the area under the plasma concentration-time profile (AUC) for animal species
 641 and humans will be obtained from all the then available publications or other sources: after adjusting
 642 for the same dose and assuming linear kinetics, the ratio of the AUCs in animal species and humans
 643 will be calculated. This factor, the HEDF, will be used to convert the doses in the animal studies to the
 644 corresponding human doses, thus enabling to compare the doses at which effects are observed in
 645 various species.

646 For the calculation of the HEDFs in the EFSA CEF Panel opinion in 2015, the AUC in humans was
 647 derived from PBPK-simulation. In view of the BPA re-evaluation new toxicokinetic studies with BPA in
 648 human volunteers have become available and these will be used for determining the AUC in humans.
 649 Similarly, new toxicokinetic data in animals, if any, will be considered for AUC determinations. The
 650 HEDFs will be established in accordance with the new knowledge on the kinetics of BPA in humans
 651 and/or animals.

652 As defined in the EFSA Scientific Committee draft guidance (2017a) "A WoE assessment is a process
653 in which evidence is integrated to determine the relative support for possible answers to a question".
654 That guidance considers the WoE assessment as comprising three basic steps: (i) assembling the
655 evidence, (ii) weighing the evidence, and (iii) integrating the evidence, as described below.

656 (i) Assembling the evidence: the experts will sort the studies according to the human or animal
657 health outcome category, *e.g.* reproductive/developmental effects.

658 All the endpoints tested in the studies referring to a certain health outcome category will
659 be either classified as "apical" endpoints (*e.g.* infertility) or "intermediate" endpoints (*e.g.*
660 anogenital distance (AGD)) by two independent reviewers specialised in the area. By
661 apical endpoint it is intended an observable outcome in a whole organism, such as a
662 clinical sign or pathologic state, that is indicative of a disease state that can result from
663 exposure to a toxicant (Krewski *et al.*, 2011). Intermediate endpoints are events occurring
664 at a step between the molecular initiating event and the apical outcome: they are
665 toxicologically relevant to the apical outcome (a necessary element of the mode of action
666 or a biomarker of effect (see *e.g.* OECD, 2008)) and are experimentally quantifiable.

667 A further sorting of the studies will also take into consideration the internal validity score
668 of the individual studies, followed by the relevance to the question judgement. To
669 summarise the evidence in animals, the animal studies addressing a given health
670 outcome/endpoint will be plotted in a single graph (see Fig. 2 as an example) containing,
671 for each study, information on the life stage of the animals at treatment onset, duration
672 of the treatment and sampling time for measurements, the doses tested, the magnitude
673 and statistical significance of the effects at any dose (filled *vs.* empty symbol), the study
674 validity tier, the rating (*i.e.* medium or high) of the study relevance to the question, and
675 the reference. As described above, all doses on the x-axis of the graph will be converted
676 into HED. The magnitude of the effects caused by BPA at each dose will be standardised
677 to the effect size in the control group to enable a comparison of the magnitude of the
678 effects across different doses and studies. The direction of the effect (increase *vs.*
679 decrease) will also be graphically represented (round *vs.* diamond shape) to compare
680 inter-study consistency.

681 Similar graphs will also be created for human studies. BPA exposure will be expressed as
682 quartiles and changes in the measured parameters will be expressed relatively to the
683 control levels.

684

685

686

687 **Figure 2:** Graphical representation of the WoE analysis in the dose range of interest

688 ii) Weighing the evidence: based on expert judgement two independent reviewers will
 689 assess the confidence in the body of evidence using this graphical approach, which could
 690 allow, for each endpoint, to obtain an overall estimation of the likelihood of an effect
 691 being observed. The issues that would need to be considered, when making such
 692 estimation are:

- 693 a. the overall internal validity of the studies that show/don't show an effect
- 694 b. the consistency of the results between different studies within the same
 695 species/population or across species/populations)
- 696 c. the dose-response relationships
- 697 d. the magnitude of the effects
- 698 e. the biological plausibility of the effects on interrelated endpoints or MoA
- 699 f. the relevance of the results to the question of interest

700 Biological plausibility is a fundamental concept for data integration across different
 701 endpoints but within a certain health outcome category as it strengthens the causal
 702 inference for a certain effect. Indeed concordance of results between different endpoints
 703 on the same biological pathway known to lead to a certain toxicity or disease state
 704 increases the confidence in the body of evidence for a certain effect. If instead there are
 705 unexplained inconsistencies in the results concerning the same biological pathway, in
 706 principle priority should be given to the evidence arising from "apical" endpoints (*i.e.*
 707 overt effect or disease state). In all study types the apical endpoints are generally
 708 considered to be the most direct, or applicable, to the assessment of the health outcome
 709 (*e.g.* incidence of cancer of the mammary gland). Intermediate endpoints are relevant
 710 and can include key events, upstream indicators, risk factors, intermediate outcomes or
 711 measures related to the final endpoints, *e.g.* pre-neoplastic lesions. However, it is not
 712 always agreed what an intermediate and an apical endpoint are for every toxic effect.
 713 Also in some cases, intermediate endpoints may be as decisive as apical endpoints *e.g.*
 714 when they are key events in an adverse outcome pathway; in other cases, intermediate
 715 effects may be transient and therefore not as relevant as apical endpoints. Information on
 716 MoA of the target compounds and endpoints may also support this step. MoA studies in
 717 laboratory animals can establish the key events and their relationships required for the
 718 various adverse outcomes as a result of BPA exposure.

719 The outcome of this hazard identification step will be a conclusion on the likelihood that
 720 BPA is hazardous with respect to a certain health outcome in human and/or animal
 721 studies at any BPA exposure level. The scale of likelihood will comprise 3 categories,
 722 namely "Likely", "As likely as not" and "Unlikely" (see Table 13).

723 **Table 13:** Scale of likelihood for a given health outcome category

Category of likelihood	Percentage of likelihood	Comment
"Likely"	66-100%	
"As likely as not"	33—66%	It is about equally likely that BPA causes, or does not cause, the effect.
"Unlikely"	0-33%	

724 For the purpose of the current assessment, in the absence of studies addressing the
 725 apical endpoint and in the presence of studies showing "Likely" effects on intermediate
 726 endpoints, a BPA effect in that health outcome category would be concluded to be
 727 "Likely".

728

729 iii) Integrating the evidence: the overall conclusions of the WoE analysis applied to BPA
 730 hazard identification (in the dose range of interest) will be obtained by integrating the
 731 evidence from human and/or experimental animal studies according to the scheme shown
 732 in Fig. 3.

733 Adverse effects (apical and intermediate endpoints) for human and animal studies will be identified by
 734 the Working Group performing the risk assessment taking into account the previous scientific opinion
 735 issued by the CEF Panel (2015).

736

737 * It would be unrealistic to expect being able to derive a likelihood of "unlikely" from human studies on BPA-
 738 environmentally exposed subjects, however for consistency and to ease the understanding of the graph, this situation
 was included

739 **Figure 3:** Integrating the evidence from human and non-human animal studies

740

741 In the WoE approach, findings in animal studies have to be integrated with those in human studies.
 742 The integration of such findings follows the process described in Fig. 3.

743 The results of human studies are the most directly applicable to human health. Therefore findings in
 744 human studies with the level of evidence "Likely" will be rated as "Likely" in the final judgement
 745 irrespective of the outcome of the animal studies (Fig. 3). The same will apply for "Unlikely" effects in
 746 humans which will predominate over animal evidence except in the case of "Likely" effects in animals
 747 which will be treated on a case by case basis.

748 The "Likely" effects in animal studies will determine the final integrated human/animal likelihood
 749 judgement irrespective of whether human data is missing or judged "As likely as not" (Fig. 3).

750 If findings from animal studies indicate an “Unlikely” effect and (i) the evidence from human studies is
751 “As likely as not” , the reviewers will conclude on an overall result of “As likely as not”, while (ii) if
752 there is missing data for humans the overall rating in the WoE will be “Unlikely”.

753 **9. Relevance and adversity of the effect for human health**

754 An effect is considered “adverse” when leading to a change in the morphology, physiology, growth,
755 development, reproduction or life span of an organism, system or (sub)population that results in an
756 impairment of functional capacity to compensate for additional stress or an increase in susceptibility to
757 other influences” (WHO, 2009).

758 Once the likelihood that BPA is hazardous has been assessed with respect to certain toxicological
759 endpoints according to the overall body of evidence, the next step will be the assessment of the
760 relevance of those effects seen in animal studies to human health and their adversity in humans, if
761 they occur.

762 While relevance to humans is intrinsic in human studies, adversity of effects will be evaluated case-by-
763 case by the experts performing the hazard assessment.

764 This evaluation will be performed by applying expert judgement, ensuring that a justification for the
765 decision on the relevance and adversity is provided.

766 **10. Method for performing hazard characterisation**

767 By hazard characterisation it is intended the analysis of the dose-response relationship and the
768 identification of a reference point (a benchmark dose (BMD), its lower confidence limit (BMDL) for a
769 particular incidence/size of effect or a NOAEL) as a basis for a new TDI. Hazard characterisation will
770 be performed for “Likely” effects (as assessed through the WoE analysis), using human or animal
771 studies (depending on data availability and study appraisal outcome) showing adverse effects relevant
772 to humans.

773 The animal studies supporting “Likely” effects that have been assigned relatively higher relevance and
774 internal validity and include at least three test doses, will undergo such dose-response analysis. The
775 lowest reference point will be considered for the possible derivation of a TDI.

776 *In vivo* studies considered not directly suitable for the derivation of the reference point and supporting
777 “Likely” or “As likely as not” effects will be collectively considered in an uncertainty analysis, to
778 possibly define the need of an extra factor to cover for uncertainties in the BPA database at low levels
779 of exposure.

780 For human studies, due to methodological constraints, exposure can only be estimated by the sum of
781 urinary conjugated and unconjugated BPA concentrations. These cannot be directly related to an
782 internal/systemic concentration of the endocrine active fraction of BPA. The latter, which is the
783 toxicologically relevant concentration for a reference point, highly depends on the route of exposure,
784 *i.e.* oral *vs.* dermal. When possible, a dose – response relationship will be established and a reference
785 point derived by appropriate statistical methods for human studies. Whereas there is no need for an
786 inter-species assessment factor when using human data for deriving a TDI, an intra-species factor
787 could be needed to adjust the observation for the whole population. An additional uncertainty factor
788 might also be necessary to cover for uncertainty in the database.

789 For the human hazard characterisation, data on the toxicokinetics (ADME and PBPK modelling) will
790 support the extrapolation of results from experimental animal studies to humans. This information is
791 also important to determine which uncertainty factors have to be applied when establishing the
792 health-based guidance value. It should be noted that the default factor of 4 for interspecies kinetic
793 differences is already taken into consideration by the chemical-specific approach in which the ratio of
794 AUCs in animals to the AUC in humans is used to adjust the external doses in animals to the external
795 doses in humans. The remaining uncertainty factor should cover for inter-species difference in
796 toxicodynamics (default factor is 2.5) and inter-individual variability in both toxicokinetics and
797 toxicodynamics (the default factor being 10).

798

799 **11. Methods for addressing the uncertainties**

800 The evaluation of the inherent uncertainties will be performed in accordance with the upcoming EFSA
801 Guidance on Uncertainty in EFSA Scientific Assessment of the EFSA Scientific Committee, which is
802 currently published in its draft form (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017b). According to the draft
803 Guidance, uncertainty is used as a general term referring to all types of limitations in the knowledge
804 available at the time an assessment is conducted and within the time and resources agreed for the
805 assessment. Furthermore the draft Guidance recommends using quantitative expressions of
806 uncertainty through verbal terms with quantitative definitions.

807 Several proposals are given in the draft Guidance on how the assessment of uncertainty could be
808 performed. For the hazard characterisation step of BPA assessment, the informal expert knowledge
809 elicitation could be the most appropriate for consistency and integration of the re-evaluation of BPA
810 with the former BPA assessment (CEF Panel, 2015) where a quantitative uncertainty analysis was
811 performed.

812 The procedure should follow the minimal requirements with pre-defined questions and a pre-defined
813 expert board; the process should be fully documented. The result of the uncertainty analysis will be a
814 description of additional uncertainties not already covered in the form of subjective probabilities.

815

DRAFT

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883 **Abbreviations**

884

ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism And Excretion
AUC	Area Under The Curve
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose (Lower Confidence Limit)
BMDL10	Benchmark Dose (10% Lower Confidence Limit)
BMI	Body Mass Index
BPA	Bisphenol A
CEF Panel	Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings And Processing Aids
CI	Confidence Interval
EC	European Commission
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
FAO	Food And Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GLP	Good Laboratory Practices
HED	Human Equivalent Dose
HEDF	Human Equivalent Dose Factor
LOAEL	Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level
LOEL	Lowest Observed Effect Level
MOA	Mode of Action
NOAEL	No Observed Adverse Effect Level
NOEL	No Observed Effect Level
NTP	National Toxicology Programme
OHAT	Office of Health Assessment and Translation
PBPK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Modelling
Prometheus	Promoting Methods for Evidence Use in Science
ROB	Risk of Bias
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
t-TDI	Temporary- Tolerable Daily Intake
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
WHO	World Health Organisation
WoE	Weight of Evidence

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Appendix A – Search strings used for each database

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888 Information sources

Information source	Platform	Dates
PubMed	National Library of Medicine	2013-present
Scopus	Scopus	2013-present
Web of Science Core Collection. Science Citation Expanded Index	Web of Science	2013-present
Web of Science Core Collection. Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)	Web of Science	2015-present
Web of Science Core Collection. Current Chemical Reactions (CCR-EXPANDED)	Web of Science	2013-present
Web of Science Core Collection. Index Chemicus (IC)	Web of Science	2013-present
DART	Toxnet	2013-present
TOXLINE	Toxnet	2013-present

889

890 Search strategies

891 PubMed

Search	Query
#4	Search #1 NOT #2 Filters: Publication date from 2013/01/01
#3	Search #1 NOT #2
#2	Search "Comment" [Publication Type] OR "Editorial" [Publication Type] OR "Letter" [Publication Type]
#1	Search "bisphenol A" [Supplementary Concept] OR "bisphenol A"[tiab] OR BPA[tiab] OR "80 05 7"[tiab] OR "201 245 8"[tiab]

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893 Scopus

Search	Query
#5	(CASREGNUMBER (80-05-7)) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("bisphenol a" OR bpa OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8")) AND (PUBYEAR > 2012) AND (EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "ch") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "le") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE , "ed"))
#4	(CASREGNUMBER (80-05-7)) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("bisphenol a" OR bpa OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8")) AND (PUBYEAR > 2012)
#3	(CASREGNUMBER (80-05-7)) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("bisphenol a" OR bpa OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8"))
#2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("bisphenol a" OR bpa OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8")
#1	CASREGNUMBER (80-05-7)

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897 Web of Science Core Collection:

- 898
- Science Citation Expanded Index
- 899
- Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)
- 900
- Current Chemical Reactions (CCR-EXPANDED)
- 901
- Index Chemicus (IC)

Search	Query
#2	TS=("bisphenol A" OR BPA OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8") Refined by: [excluding] DOCUMENT TYPES: (NEWS ITEM OR EDITORIAL MATERIAL OR MEETING ABSTRACT OR LETTER OR BOOK CHAPTER) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC Timespan=2013-20XX
#1	TS=("bisphenol A" OR BPA OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8") Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC Timespan=2013-20XX

902

903 DART

904

Search	Query
# 1	(80-05-7 [rn] OR "bisphenol a" OR bpa OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8") AND 2013:20XX [yr]

905

906 TOXLINE

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Search	Query
# 1	(80-05-7 [rn] OR "bisphenol a" OR bpa OR "80 05 7" OR "201 245 8") AND 2013:20XX [yr]

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Appendix B – Guidelines for the assessment of quality

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B.1. Human case-control studies

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Question n°	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
1 Key question A	Domain: Detection Can we be confident in the exposure characterisation?	++	There is direct evidence that the exposure was assessed using well-established methods that directly measure exposure (<i>e.g.</i> measurement of the chemical in the environment or measurement of the chemical in blood, plasma, urine, <i>etc.</i>), OR exposure was assessed using less-established methods that directly measure exposure and are validated against well-established methods.
		+	There is indirect evidence that the exposure was assessed using well-established methods that directly measure exposure (<i>e.g.</i> measurement of the chemical in the environment or measurement of the chemical in blood, plasma, urine, <i>etc.</i>), OR exposure was assessed using indirect measures (<i>e.g.</i> questionnaire or occupational exposure assessment by a certified industrial hygienist) that have been validated or empirically shown to be consistent with methods that directly measure exposure (<i>i.e.</i> inter-methods validation: one method <i>vs.</i> another).
		-	There is indirect evidence that the exposure was assessed using poorly validated methods that directly measure exposure, OR there is direct evidence that the exposure was assessed using indirect measures that have not been validated or empirically shown to be consistent with methods that directly measure exposure (<i>e.g.</i> a job-exposure matrix or self-report without validation) (record "NR" as basis for answer), OR there is insufficient information provided about the method used for exposure assessment (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that the exposure was assessed using poorly validated methods, OR there is evidence of exposure misclassification (<i>e.g.</i> differential recall of self-reported exposure).
2 Key question B	Domain: Detection Can we be confident in the outcome Assessment?	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases (<i>i.e.</i> case definition) using well-established methods (the gold standard).
		+	There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases (<i>i.e.</i> case definition) using acceptable methods, AND subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all study groups, OR it is deemed that the outcome assessment methods used would not appreciably bias results.
		-	There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases (<i>i.e.</i> case definition) using non acceptable methods, OR there is insufficient information provided about how cases were identified (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases (<i>i.e.</i> case definition) using non-acceptable methods.

3 Key question C	Domain: Exposure Was the time-window between exposure and outcome assessment appropriate?	++	There is direct evidence that the time window was appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
		+	There is indirect evidence that the time window was appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
		-	There is indirect evidence that the time window was not appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
		--	There is direct evidence that the time window was not appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
4	Domain: Others Do the statistical methods seem appropriate?	++	The statistical methods have been described with enough detail and do seem appropriate, usual or familiar, (<i>i.e.</i> details on preliminary analyses to modify raw data before have been provided; variables used in the primary analyses are clearly identified and summarized with descriptive statistics; main methods for analyzing the primary objectives of the study are fully described; conformity of data to the assumptions of the test used to analyze them are verified; whether and how any allowance or adjustments were made for multiple comparisons have been indicated; if relevant, how any outlying data were treated in the analysis have been reported; whether tests were one- or two-tailed have been specified and use of one-tailed tests has been justified; alpha level (<i>e.g.</i> 0.05) that defines statistical significance has been reported; references for the statistical methods have been provided; the statistical software used has been specified).
		+	The statistical methods have not been described in detail, AND there is indirect evidence that statistical methods are appropriate, usual or familiar.
		-	The statistical methods have not been described in detail, AND there is indirect evidence that statistical methods are inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar.
		--	The statistical methods have not been described in detail, AND there is direct evidence that statistical methods are inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar.

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919 **B.2. Human cohort studies**

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Question n°	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
1 Key question A	Domain: Detection Can we be confident in the exposure characterisation?	++	There is direct evidence that the exposure was assessed using well-established methods that directly measure exposure (<i>e.g.</i> measurement of the chemical in the environment or measurement of the chemical in blood, plasma, urine, <i>etc.</i>), OR exposure was assessed using less-established methods that directly measure exposure and are validated against well-established methods.
		+	There is indirect evidence that the exposure was assessed using well-established methods that directly measure exposure (<i>e.g.</i> measurement of the chemical in the environment or measurement of the chemical in blood, plasma, urine, <i>etc.</i>), OR exposure was assessed using indirect measures (<i>e.g.</i> questionnaire or occupational exposure assessment by a certified industrial hygienist) that have been validated or empirically shown to be consistent with methods that directly measure exposure (<i>i.e.</i> inter-methods validation: one method <i>vs.</i> another).
		-	There is indirect evidence that the exposure was assessed using poorly validated methods that directly measure exposure, OR there is direct evidence that the exposure was assessed using indirect measures that have not been validated or empirically shown to be consistent with methods that directly measure exposure (<i>e.g.</i> a job-exposure matrix or self-report without validation) (record "NR" as basis for answer), OR there is insufficient information provided about the method used for exposure assessment (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that the exposure was assessed using poorly validated methods, OR evidence of exposure misclassification (<i>e.g.</i> differential recall of self-reported exposure).
2 Key question B	Domain: Detection Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed using well-established methods (the gold standard).
		+	There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed using acceptable methods, OR it is deemed that the outcome assessment methods used would not appreciably bias results.
		-	There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed using a non-acceptable method (<i>e.g.</i> a questionnaire used to assess outcomes with no information on validation), OR there is insufficient information provided about the outcome assessment method (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed using a non-acceptable method.
3 Key question C	Domain: Exposure Was the time-window between exposure and	++	There is direct evidence that the time window was appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
		+	There is indirect evidence that the time window was appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
		-	There is indirect evidence that the time window was not appropriate for the endpoint of interest.

Question n°	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
	outcome assessment appropriate?	--	There is direct evidence that the time window was not appropriate for the endpoint of interest.
4	Domain: Others Do the statistical methods seem appropriate?	++	The statistical methods have been described with enough detail and do seem appropriate, usual or familiar <i>(i.e. details on preliminary analyses to modify raw data before have been provided; variables used in the primary analyses are clearly identified and summarized with descriptive statistics; main methods for analysing the primary objectives of the study are fully described; conformity of data to the assumptions of the test used to analyse them are verified; whether and how any allowance or adjustments were made for multiple comparisons have been indicated; if relevant, how any outlying data were treated in the analysis have been reported; whether tests were one- or two-tailed have been specified and use of one-tailed tests has been justified; alpha level (e.g. 0.05) that defines statistical significance has been reported; references for the statistical methods have been provided; the statistical software used has been specified).</i>
		+	The statistical methods have not been described in detail, AND there is indirect evidence that statistical methods are appropriate, usual or familiar.
		-	The statistical methods have not been described in detail, AND there is indirect evidence that statistical methods are inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar.
		--	The statistical methods have not been described in detail, AND there is direct evidence that statistical methods are inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar.

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923 **B.3. Animal experimental studies**

Question	Explanation
<p>1. The test compound was unlikely to contain any impurities that may significantly have affected its toxicity.</p>	<p>The purity of the test compound can potentially affect study results. Purity is also an important aspect to consider in terms of the relevance of the test compound to the compound being risk assessed. Ideally, the test chemical should be of the highest available purity.</p> <p>Significant impurities, or isomers of the test compound, are more likely to be present, and/or to impact toxicity for certain compounds. The measured toxicity of the test compound may then be due to the contaminant. In such cases information about the level of purity and composition is critical.</p> <p>How to judge this criterion:</p> <p>Fulfilled – The test compound has been clearly identified and characterized and is of sufficient purity.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – The purity of the test compound has not been described and no information about its source is available, but it is assumed that it is unlikely that impurities are present that would significantly affect the results of the study.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – The test compound is likely to contain impurities that can affect study results</p>
<p>2. A concurrent negative control group was included.</p> <p>Key aspect A</p>	<p>A concurrent negative control group should always be included as it is critical for determining treatment-related effects. The negative control group can be either untreated or vehicle-treated. However, in studies where a vehicle is used to administer the test compound it is critical that a vehicle-treated control group is included. In certain cases, it may be useful to also include a completely untreated group for identification of any influence on results from the vehicle.</p> <p>Historical control data from the same laboratory using the same methods and relating to animals of the same strain, age and sex, and supplier, as those used in the study may be very useful. However, such data should not provide the only negative control data for statistical analyses as biological parameters in laboratory animals can vary significantly over time. Therefore, if a study includes only historical negative control data this criterion should be judged as “not fulfilled”.</p> <p>How to judge this criterion:</p> <p>Fulfilled – a concurrent negative (vehicle-treated) control group was included.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – no negative control was included or only a historical negative control was referred to.</p>
<p>3. A reliable and sensitive animal model was used for investigating the test compound and selected endpoints.</p> <p>Key aspect B</p>	<p>The choice of animal model (test species, strain, sex, etc.) is based on a number of considerations, including knowledge regarding species differences in terms of pharmacology, repeat-dose toxicology, metabolism, toxicokinetics and route of administration. Rodents (rats or mice) are commonly recommended for <i>in vivo</i> testing in current OECD test guidelines and are well characterized in terms of the reliability and sensitivity, as well as relevance to humans of different biological parameters and endpoints. Thus, it is specifically important that the study authors have justified their choice of animal model if other species have been used. It should be noted that, for investigation of certain endpoints, other species may be more sensitive and preferable. For example, rabbits are commonly recommended for teratology studies (OECD 2008). Similarly, available information about species differences in the toxicokinetics of a compound may warrant testing in a specific species. The evaluator is referred to regulatory test guidelines (e.g. OECD or US EPA) for discussions of the most appropriate test species for different study types.</p> <p>Reliability, in this context, refers to whether the animal model has been shown to generate reproducible results for the type of endpoints investigated.</p> <p>The sensitivity of the animal model relates to the ability to detect changes in the endpoints investigated in the model.</p> <p>Fulfilled – The animal model used is not suspected to be insensitive or unreliable.</p>

	<p>Not fulfilled – there is available information that indicates that the animal model is either insensitive or clearly unreliable for studying the test compound or for investigating the endpoints considered. Or the expected outcome is lacking from concurrent positive controls, if included, indicating that the test methods or animal model is insensitive.</p>
<p>4. Animals were individually identified.</p>	<p>In order to ensure reliable administration of the test compound, allocation to treatment groups and different tests, as well as recording of observations and test results, it is important that animals are individually identified.</p> <p>Fulfilled – it is stated that animals were individually identified; the specific method for identification does not have to be described.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – it is not clearly stated whether or not animals were individually identified, but it may be inferred from other information reported for the study design and conduct</p> <p>Not fulfilled – it is stated that animals were not individually identified, or this can be inferred from other information reported for the study design and conduct.</p>
<p>5. Housing conditions (temperature, relative humidity, light-dark cycle) were appropriate for the study type and animal model.</p>	<p>Housing conditions and handling may influence animal behaviour and physiological response to stress and, consequently, study results. Importantly, variability in housing conditions may lead to increased variability in results and decreased sensitivity of the tests conducted.</p> <p>Different housing conditions apply to different species and different types of studies. Descriptions of standard conditions may for example be found in OECD test guidelines relevant to different types of studies and in corresponding guidance documents (http://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/testing/oecdguidelinesforthetestingofchemicals.htm). Guidance is also provided in the US National Research Council's "Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals" (https://grants.nih.gov/grants/olaw/Guide-for-the-Care-and-use-of-laboratory-animals.pdf)</p> <p>Housing conditions are often incompletely reported in studies published in the peer-reviewed literature, therefore it might be useful to keep in mind that this criterion may often be judged as partially fulfilled for such studies, and the impact of lack of reporting on total study reliability should be carefully considered.</p> <p>Fulfilled – housing conditions have been fully described and were in line with standard recommendations relevant to the study type and animal model.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – some of the housing conditions were in line with standard recommendations relevant to the study type and animal model. Others deviated from standard recommendations or were not reported.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – all housing conditions deviated from standard recommendations relevant to the study type and animal model.</p>
<p>6. The number of animals per sex in each cage were appropriate for the study type and animal model</p>	<p>The number of animals housed together may have an effect on behavior and other biological parameters. Generally, laboratory animals should be housed in pairs or groups, unless the species is naturally solitary. Crowding should also be avoided as it induces stress that affects <i>e.g.</i> hormone levels and development.</p> <p>Scientific and practical aspects connected to the type of study influence how animals are housed together. Recommendations and requirements for the number of animals per cage relevant for different study types can be found in OECD test guidelines and corresponding guidance documents. Single housing may be recommended in some cases, <i>e.g.</i> in acute toxicity tests and in inhalation studies using aerosol exposure. Individual housing may also be necessary <i>e.g.</i> for pregnant dams and for males after mating, as well as during certain procedures, such as the use of metabolism cages. When applied, single housing should be restricted to the shortest time possible (Morton and Hau 2011).</p> <p>Standardisation of litter size by culling is sometimes conducted. Descriptions and recommendations for this procedure are provided in OECD test guidelines for developmental toxicity studies.</p> <p>Fulfilled – the number of animals per sex and cage were in line with standard recommendations relevant to the study type and animal model.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – the number of animals per cage deviated somewhat from standard</p>

	<p>recommendations relevant to the study type and animal model, however scientific and/or practical justifications for these deviations were provided.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – the number of animals per cage deviated significantly from standard recommendations relevant to the study type and animal model and no scientific or practical justification was provided.</p>
<p>7. The test system is unlikely to contain contaminants that could affect the study results, such as phytoestrogens and estrogenic contamination.</p>	<p>Materials used in cages, water bottles and any physical enrichment should be considered, <i>e.g.</i> in terms of releasing substances that may affect study results. It should be ensured as far as possible that feed and drinking water are free from phytoestrogens and estrogenic substances. Phytoestrogen content is specifically critical in studies where endocrine activity/disruption is being investigated. For guidance on appropriate phytoestrogen levels in feed see <i>e.g.</i> OECD TG 440 (OECD 2007b). Ideally, feed and water should be tested for the presence of contaminants and phytoestrogens. Similarly, the bedding material should be considered, especially if endocrine activity/disruption is being investigated, since it may contain naturally occurring estrogenic or antiestrogenic substances. <i>E.g.</i> corn cob appears to be antiestrogenic and affects cyclicity in rats (OECD 2007b). Specifically, phytoestrogen content should be minimized in the bedding material in these cases.</p> <p>A full report of possible contaminants is seldom provided in studies published in the peer-reviewed literature, therefore it might be useful to keep in mind that this criterion may often be judged as partially fulfilled for such studies, and the impact of lack of reporting on total study reliability should be carefully considered.</p> <p>Fulfilled – no contaminants that could have influenced study results are suspected and/or feed, water, bedding and other materials have been analyzed and controlled for relevant contaminants.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – some contaminants have been controlled for or analyzed but there may potentially be other contaminants present.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – it is likely that the test system was contaminated in a way that could affect study results, <i>e.g.</i> a bedding material known to contain estrogenic or antiestrogenic substances was used in a study investigating endocrine endpoints.</p>
<p>8. An adequate number of dose levels was used.</p>	<p>Fulfilled – Three or more dose levels were used.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – Two dose levels were used.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – One dose level was used.</p>
<p>9. The timing and duration of administration do not seem to be inappropriate for investigating the included endpoints.</p> <p>Key aspect C</p>	<p>OECD test guidelines and corresponding guidance provide recommendations for timing and duration of administration of the test compound for different types of studies. In general, the dosing regimen should “maximise the sensitivity of the test without significantly altering the accuracy and interpretability of the biological data obtained” (OECD 2002b). Timing and duration should be considered specifically in terms of covering sensitive periods of development (<i>e.g.</i> “period of male sexual differentiation in late gestation” (OECD 2008)). In certain cases, it is also relevant to consider timing of administration in relation to when measurements of toxicological outcomes are conducted. For example, when investigating effects on behavior the potential of the administration to produce acute effects on behavioral measures should be considered, especially where the test substance is administered directly to offspring daily (OECD 2008).</p> <p>Fulfilled – the timing and duration of administration of the test compound is in line with general recommendations for the study type, is not likely to interfere with the measurements conducted, and cover sensitive periods of development, where relevant.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – the timing and duration of administration of the test compound deviates somewhat from standard recommendations, however a scientific or practical justification is provided and sensitive periods of development are covered.</p> <p>Not fulfilled - the timing and duration of administration of the test compound is significantly different from general recommendations for the study type without being</p>

	justified, and/or is likely to directly interfere with toxicological outcomes/measurements, and/or do not cover sensitive periods of development, where relevant.
<p>10. Reliable and sensitive test methods were used for investigating the selected endpoints.</p> <p>Key aspect D</p>	<p>The reliability of the methods refers to whether they are known to generate reproducible results for the type of endpoints investigated, <i>e.g.</i> if the methods have been validated across different laboratories.</p> <p>The sensitivity of the methods relates to the ability to detect changes in the endpoints investigated.</p> <p>Studies conducted according to standardized and validated test guidelines (such as OECD test guidelines) are often considered to be reliable and adequate for risk assessment. However, it is important to keep in mind that adherence to standardized test guidelines does not automatically ensure the sensitivity of the methods applied. Further, sensitivity of the methods may in some cases be influenced by how the protocols are utilized (OECD 2008).</p> <p>Fulfilled – there is no information that suggests that the test methods are insensitive or unreliable in this context.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – it is suspected that one or more of the methods applied may be insensitive or unreliable.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – there is available information that indicates that one or more of the methods applied is either insensitive or clearly unreliable for studies of the test compound or for investigating the endpoints considered. Or the expected outcome is lacking from concurrent positive controls, if included, indicating that the methods or animal model is insensitive.</p>
<p>11. Measurements do not seem to have been collected at unsuitable time points in order to generate sensitive, valid and reliable data.</p> <p>Key aspect E</p>	<p>This criterion covers several aspects concerning the timing of measurements and collection of data.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data should be collected at the relevant time point in relation to the time needed to detect treatment related effects. In regard to specific developmental effects, these may only become apparent at a certain age, relating <i>e.g.</i> to behavioral ontogeny or onset of puberty. In addition, the time point for measurements and data collection should be chosen to avoid influence from any acute effects of the test substance administration (OECD 2008). OECD test guidelines provide recommendations for the timing of measurements and data collection in different study types. 2. Data should be collected so that the time of day does not influence measurements. For example, responses in behavioral testing in nocturnal animals like mice and rats is likely to produce different behavior during the day than during the night. For such reasons reversed lighting conditions may be applied to test nocturnal animals during the day. <p>Fulfilled – The timing of tests and measurements were appropriate to detect sensitive effects and there are no related aspects that are likely to influence the reliability of the results.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – Some, but not all, aspects of timing were appropriate. Importantly, there are no critical issues that raise concern,</p> <p>Not fulfilled - The timing of tests and measurements were not appropriate. <i>E.g.</i> it is likely that sensitive treatment related effects have been missed, or there are other aspects that are likely to have influenced the reliability of the results,</p>
<p>12. The statistical methods have been clearly described and do not seem inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar and a sufficient number</p>	<p>The choice of statistical analyses will depend on the type of study and the nature of the endpoints measured. OECD test guidelines and corresponding guidance documents provide some recommendations for statistical tests (<i>e.g.</i> Appendix IV of OECD's Guidance notes for analysis and evaluation of chronic toxicity and carcinogenicity studies, OECD 2002b) as well as for considerations to be made in statistical analyses of different types of tests. Evaluation of this criterion also includes considering if the correct statistical unit was used. For example, it is generally recommended that the litter (or dam) is the statistical unit in developmental toxicity studies to account for litter effects. Correlations across litter mates due to genetic and/or prenatal conditions can have considerable influence on the statistical</p>

<p>of animals per dose group was used</p> <p>Key aspect F</p>	<p>significance of results (<i>e.g.</i> Holson <i>et al.</i> 2008; Li <i>et al.</i> 2008). To control for litter effects, either only one pup per sex and litter is submitted to each test/measurement in the study, or all pups are examined and litter effects are accounted for in the statistical analyses. For certain endpoints, <i>e.g.</i> malformations, it might be warranted to examine all pups as it increases the statistical power and not all pups are identical.</p> <p>Similarly, examining many pups per litter greatly enhances the ability to detect low dose effects (OECD 2008). The size of litter effect varies depending on endpoint measured, dose (being larger at high dose levels), and chemical mode of action.</p> <p>In general, normality of the data should have been checked and the choice of parametric or non-parametric tests should have been based upon that result.</p> <p>Sample size should be large enough to ensure sufficient statistical power to detect any effects in the endpoints measured. This includes considerations of the background incidence and variability of the measured effects, as well as the method of analysis.</p> <p>Excessive losses of animals in treatment groups that could affect statistical power should be noted.</p> <p>OECD test guidelines provide recommendations for number of animals per treatment group for different study types and endpoint measurements. However, primary consideration should be given to justifications for sample size provided by study authors, if stated.</p> <p>Fulfilled – The statistical methods have been clearly described and do not seem inappropriate, unusual or unfamiliar.</p> <p>AND a sufficient number of animals was included in the different treatment groups and loss of animals during the study is not likely to have substantially affected statistical power.</p> <p>Partially fulfilled – Unusual or unfamiliar methods were applied in the statistical analyses but do not seem clearly inappropriate.</p> <p>AND/OR a lower than usual number of animals was used, which may have caused lower sensitivity/statistical power of the study.</p> <p>Not fulfilled – No statistical tests were used, or the tests used are clearly inappropriate for the study type and/or endpoints measured.</p> <p>AND/OR the number of animals in each treatment group was clearly insufficient or there was substantial loss of animals during the study that may have affected statistical power.</p>
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Appendix C – Guidelines for the assessment of risk of bias

926 C.1. Human case-control studies

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Question n°	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
1 Key question A	Domain: Selection Did selection of study participants result in appropriate comparison groups?	++	There is direct evidence that cases and controls were similar (<i>e.g.</i> recruited from the same eligible population, with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age, gender, ethnicity), recruited within the same time frame, and both cases and controls are described as having no history of the outcome. Note: A study will be considered at low risk of bias if baseline characteristics of the two comparison groups are not statistically different.
		+	There is indirect evidence that cases and controls were similar (<i>e.g.</i> recruited from the same eligible population, with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age, gender and ethnicity), recruited within the same time frame, and both cases and controls are described as having no history of the outcome, OR differences between cases and controls are limited and would not appreciably bias the results.
		-	There is indirect evidence that controls were drawn from a very dissimilar population than cases or recruited within very different time frames, OR there is insufficient information provided about the appropriateness of controls (including rate of response reported for cases only).
		--	There is direct evidence that controls were drawn from a very dissimilar population than cases or recruited within very different time frames.
2 Key question B	Domain: Confounding Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables?	++	There is direct evidence that appropriate adjustments were made for primary covariates and confounders (including other exposures, if relevant) in the final analyses through the use of statistical models to reduce specific bias (including standardisation, matching of cases and controls, adjustment in multivariate model, stratification, propensity scoring, or other methods were appropriately justified). Acceptable consideration of appropriate adjustment factors includes cases when the factor is not included in the final adjustment model because the author conducted analyses that indicated it did not need to be included, AND there is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements.
		+	There is indirect evidence that appropriate adjustments (including other exposures, if relevant) were made, OR it is deemed that not considering or only considering a partial list of covariates or confounders (including other exposures) in the final analyses would not appreciably bias results. AND there is evidence (direct or indirect) that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements, OR it is deemed that the measures used would not appreciably bias results (<i>i.e.</i> the authors justified the validity of the measures from previously published research).

		-	There is indirect evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders (including other exposures) differed between cases and controls and was not investigated further, OR there is insufficient information provided about the distribution of known confounders (including other exposures) in cases and controls (record "NR" as basis for answer), OR there is indirect evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using measurements of unknown validity.
		--	There is direct evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders (including other exposures) differed between cases and controls, confounding was demonstrated, but was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses, OR there is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using non valid measurements.
3	Domain: Attrition Were outcome data completely reported without attrition or exclusion from analysis?	++	There is direct evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was adequately addressed, and reasons were documented when subjects were removed from the study or excluded from analyses.
		+	There is indirect evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was adequately addressed, and reasons were documented when subjects were removed from the study or excluded from analyses.
		-	There is indirect evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was not adequately addressed, OR there is insufficient information provided about why subjects were removed from the study or excluded from analyses (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of subject exclusion from analyses includes: reason for exclusion likely to be related to true outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for exclusion across study groups.
4	Domain: Detection Was the exposure characterised consistently across study groups?	++	There is direct evidence that exposure was consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under the same method and time-frame) across groups.
		+	There is indirect evidence that exposure was consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under the same method and time-frame) across groups. OR it is deemed that an inconsistent assessment of the exposure (<i>i.e.</i> under different methods and time-frames) across groups would not considerably bias the results.
		-	There is indirect evidence that exposure was not consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under different methods and time-frames) across groups. OR there is insufficient information provided about the consistency of the exposure assessment (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that exposure was not consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under different methods and time-frames) across groups.
5	Domain: Detection Was the blinding applied and measurement consistent across study groups?	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the exposure level.
		+	There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the exposure level when reporting outcomes, OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were likely not aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome or lack of blinding is unlikely to bias a particular outcome).

		-	There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors to infer the exposure level prior to reporting outcomes (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were likely aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome), OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that outcome assessors were aware of the exposure level prior to reporting outcomes (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome).
6	Domain: Selective reporting Were all measured outcomes reported?	++	There is direct evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported. This would include outcomes reported with sufficient detail to be included in meta-analysis or fully tabulated during data extraction and analyses had been planned in advance.
		+	There is indirect evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported, OR analyses that had not been planned in advance (<i>i.e.</i> unplanned subgroup analyses) are clearly indicated as such and it is deemed that the unplanned analyses were appropriate and selective reporting would not appreciably bias results (<i>e.g.</i> appropriate analyses of an unexpected effect). This would include outcomes reported with insufficient detail such as only reporting that results were statistically significant (or not).
		-	There is indirect evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported, OR and there is indirect evidence that unplanned analyses were included that may appreciably bias results, OR there is insufficient information provided about selective outcome reporting (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported. In addition to not reporting outcomes, this would include reporting outcomes based on composite score without individual outcome components or outcomes reported using measurements, analysis methods or subsets of the data (<i>e.g.</i> subscales) that were not pre-specified or reporting outcomes not pre-specified, or that unplanned analyses were included that would appreciably bias results.

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930 **C.2. Human cohort studies**

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Question n°	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
1 Key question A	Domain: Selection Did selection of study participants result in appropriate comparison groups?	++	There is direct evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were similar (<i>e.g.</i> recruited from the same eligible population, recruited with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age and health status), recruited within the same time frame, and had the similar participation/response rates. Note: A study will be considered at low risk of bias if baseline characteristics of exposure groups are not statistically different.
		+	There is indirect evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were similar (<i>e.g.</i> recruited from the same eligible population, recruited with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age and health status), recruited within the same time frame, and had the similar participation/response rates OR differences between exposure groups would not appreciably bias results.
		-	There is indirect evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were not similar, recruited within very different time frames, or had very different participation/response rates OR there is insufficient information provided about the comparison group including a different rate of non-response without an explanation (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were not similar, recruited within very different time frames, or had very different participation/response rates.
2 Key question B	Domain: Confounding Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables?	++	There is direct evidence that appropriate adjustments or explicit considerations were made for primary covariates and confounders (including other exposures, if relevant) in the final analyses through the use of statistical models to reduce specific bias (including standardisation, matching, adjustment in multivariate model, stratification, propensity scoring, or other methods that were appropriately justified). Acceptable consideration of appropriate adjustment factors includes cases when the factor is not included in the final adjustment model because the author conducted analyses that indicated it did not need to be included, AND there is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements.
		+	There is indirect evidence that appropriate adjustments (including other exposures, if relevant) were made, OR it is deemed that not considering or only considering a partial list of covariates or confounders (including other exposures) in the final analyses would not appreciably bias results. AND there is evidence (direct or indirect) that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements, OR it is deemed that the measures used would not appreciably bias results (<i>i.e.</i> the authors justified the validity of the measures from previously published research).

		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders (including other exposures) differed between the exposures groups and was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses,</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about the distribution of known confounders (including other exposures) (record "NR" as basis for answer),</p> <p>OR there is indirect evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using measurements of unknown validity.</p>
		--	<p>There is direct evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders (including other exposures) differed between the groups, confounding was demonstrated, and was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses,</p> <p>OR there is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using non valid measurements.</p>
3	<p>Domain: Attrition</p> <p>Were outcome data completely reported without attrition or exclusion from analysis?</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (<i>i.e.</i> incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study. Acceptable handling of subject attrition includes: very little missing outcome data; reasons for missing subjects unlikely to be related to outcome (for survival data, censoring unlikely to be introducing bias); missing outcome data balanced in numbers across study groups, with similar reasons for missing data,</p> <p>OR missing data have been imputed using appropriate methods and characteristics of subjects lost to follow up or with unavailable records are described in identical way and are not significantly different from those of the study participants.</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (<i>i.e.</i> incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study,</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the proportion lost to follow-up would not appreciably bias results. This would include reports of no statistical differences in characteristics of subjects lost to follow up or with unavailable records from those of the study participants. Generally, the higher the ratio of participants with missing data among participants with events, the greater potential there is for bias. For studies with a long duration of follow-up, some withdrawals for such reasons are inevitable.</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (<i>i.e.</i> incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed,</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about numbers of subjects lost to follow-up.</p>
		--	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (<i>i.e.</i> incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of subject attrition includes: reason for missing outcome data likely to be related to the outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for missing data across study groups; or potentially inappropriate application of imputation.</p>
4 Key question C	<p>Domain: Detection</p> <p>Was the outcome characterised consistently across exposure groups</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that outcome was consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under the same method and time-frame) across exposure groups.</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that outcome was consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under the same method and time-frame) across exposure groups,</p> <p>OR it is deemed that an inconsistent assessment of the outcome (<i>i.e.</i> under different methods and time-frames) across exposure groups would not considerably bias the results.</p>

		-	There is indirect evidence that outcome was not consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under different methods and time-frames) across exposure groups, OR there is insufficient information provided about the consistency of the outcome assessment (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence that outcome was not consistently assessed (<i>i.e.</i> under different methods and time-frames) exposure across groups.
5 Key question D	Domain: Detection Was the blinding applied and measurement consistent across exposure groups?	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the exposure group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes, AND subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all exposure groups.
		+	There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the exposure group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes, AND subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all exposure groups. OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results, which is more likely to apply to objective outcome measures.
		-	There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors (including study subjects if outcomes were self-reported) to infer the exposure group prior to reporting outcomes, OR the length of follow-up differed by exposure group, OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors (record "NR" as basis for answer).
		--	There is direct evidence for lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors (including study subjects if outcomes were self-reported), including no blinding or incomplete blinding, OR the length of follow-up differed by exposure group.
6	Domain: Selective reporting Were all measured outcomes reported?	++	There is direct evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported. This would include outcomes reported with sufficient detail to be included in meta-analysis or fully tabulated during data extraction and analyses had been planned in advance.
		+	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported, OR analyses that had not been planned in advance (<i>i.e.</i> unplanned subgroup analyses) are clearly indicated as such and it is deemed that the unplanned analyses were appropriate and selective reporting would not appreciably bias results (<i>e.g.</i> appropriate analyses of an unexpected effect). This would include outcomes reported with insufficient detail such as only reporting that results were statistically significant (or not).

		<p>- There is indirect evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have <i>not</i> been reported,</p> <p>OR there is indirect evidence that unplanned analyses were included that may appreciably bias results,</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about selective outcome reporting (record "NR" as basis for answer).</p>
		<p>-- There is direct evidence that all of the measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported. In addition to not reporting outcomes, this would include reporting outcomes based on composite score without individual outcome components or outcomes reported using measurements, analysis methods or subsets of the data (<i>e.g.</i> subscales) that were not pre-specified or reporting outcomes not pre-specified, or that unplanned analyses were included that would appreciably bias results.</p>

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934 C.3. Animal experimental studies

Question n°	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
1 Key question A	Domain: Selection Was administered dose or exposure level adequately randomised?	++	<p>There is direct evidence that animals were allocated to any study group including controls using a method with a random component (<i>if the study states that it was performed according to OECD test guidelines, randomisation is considered as done; please note in case the study reports that it was performed according to GLP, randomisation cannot be considered as done unless specified in other parts of the manuscript</i>).</p> <p>Note: Acceptable methods of randomisation include: referring to a random number table, using a computer random number generator, coin tossing, shuffling cards or envelopes, throwing dice, or drawing of lots (Higgins and Green 2011). Restricted randomisation (<i>e.g.</i> blocked randomisation) to ensure particular allocation ratios will be considered low risk of bias. Similarly, stratified randomisation and minimisation approaches that attempt to minimize imbalance between groups on important prognostic factors (<i>e.g.</i> body weight) will be considered acceptable. This type of approach is used by NTP, <i>i.e.</i> random number generator with body weight as a covariate.</p> <p>Note: Investigator-selection of animals from a cage is not considered random allocation because animals may not have an equal chance of being selected, <i>e.g.</i> investigator selecting animals with this method may inadvertently choose healthier, easier to catch, or less aggressive animals.</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that animals were allocated to any study group including controls using a method with a random component (<i>e.g.</i> authors state that allocation was random, without description of the method used and/or a check for baseline characteristics support this assumption),</p> <p>OR it is deemed that allocation without a clearly random component during the study would not appreciably bias results. For example, approaches such as biased coin or urn randomisation, replacement randomisation, mixed randomisation, and maximal randomisation may require consultation with a statistician to determine risk-of-bias rating (Higgins and Green 2011).</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that animals were allocated to study groups using a method with a non-random component (<i>e.g.</i> a check for baseline characteristics support this assumption),</p> <p>Note: Non-random allocation methods may be systematic, but have the potential to allow researchers to anticipate the allocation of animals to study groups (Higgins and Green 2011). Such “quasi-random” methods include investigator-selection of animals from a cage, alternation, assignment based on shipment receipt date, date of birth, or animal number.</p>
		--	<p>There is direct evidence that animals were allocated to study groups using a non-random method including judgment of the investigator, the results of a laboratory test or a series of tests (Higgins and Green 2011),</p> <p>OR there is direct evidence that baseline characteristics differ significantly between groups.</p>
2	Domain: Selection Was allocation to study group adequately	++	<p>There is direct evidence that at the time of assigning study groups the research personnel did not know what group animals were allocated to, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation until after assignment was complete and irrevocable. Acceptable methods used to ensure allocation concealment include sequentially numbered treatment containers of identical appearance or equivalent methods.</p>

	concealed	+	<p>There is indirect evidence that at the time of assigning study groups the research personnel did not know what group animals were allocated to and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation until after assignment was complete and irrevocable,</p> <p>OR it is deemed that lack of adequate allocation concealment would not appreciably affect the allocation of animals to different study groups.</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that at the time of assigning study groups it was possible for the research personnel to know what group animals were allocated to, or it is likely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation before assignment was complete and irrevocable,</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about allocation to study groups (record "NR" as basis for answer).</p>
		--	<p>There is direct evidence that at the time of assigning study groups it was possible for the research personnel to know what group animals were allocated to, or it is likely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation before assignment was complete and irrevocable.</p>
3	Domain: Performance Were experimental conditions identical across study groups?	++	<p>There is direct evidence that same vehicle was used in control and experimental animals,</p> <p>AND there is direct evidence that caregivers and/or investigators were blinded to knowledge which intervention each animal received during the experiment,</p> <p>AND there is direct evidence that non-treatment-related experimental conditions were identical across study groups (<i>i.e.</i> the study report explicitly provides this level of detail).</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the same vehicle was used in control and experimental animals,</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the vehicle used would not appreciably bias results.</p> <p>AND as described above caregivers and/or investigators are assumed to be blinded to knowledge which intervention each animal received during the experiment if authors did not report this information,</p> <p>AND as described above, identical non-treatment-related experimental conditions are assumed if authors did not report differences in housing or husbandry.</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that the vehicle differed between control and experimental animals,</p> <p>OR authors did not report the vehicle used (record "NR" as basis for answer),</p> <p>OR there is indirect evidence that that caregivers and/or investigators were not blinded to knowledge which intervention each animal received during the experiment,</p> <p>OR there is indirect evidence that non-treatment-related experimental conditions were not comparable between study groups.</p>
		--	<p>There is direct evidence from the study report that control animals were untreated, or treated with a different vehicle than experimental animals,</p> <p>OR there is direct evidence that caregivers and/or investigators were not blinded to knowledge which intervention each animal received during the experiment,</p> <p>OR there is direct evidence that non-treatment-related experimental conditions were not comparable between study groups.</p>

4 Key question B	Domain: Attrition Were outcome data completely reported without attrition or exclusion from analysis?	++	There is direct evidence that loss of animals was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when animals were removed from a study. Acceptable handling of attrition includes: very little missing outcome data; reasons for missing animals unlikely to be related to outcome (or for survival data, censoring unlikely to be introducing bias); missing outcome data balanced in numbers across study groups, with similar reasons for missing data across groups; missing outcomes is not enough to impact the effect estimate, OR missing data have been imputed using appropriate methods (ensuring that characteristics of animals are not significantly different from animals retained in the analysis).
		+	There is indirect evidence that loss of animals was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when animals were removed from a study, OR it is deemed that the proportion lost would not appreciably bias results. This would include reports of no statistical differences in characteristics of animals removed from the study from those remaining in the study.
		-	There is indirect evidence that loss of animals was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed, OR there is insufficient information provided about loss of animals (record "NR" as basis for answer). Note: Unexplained inconsistencies between materials and methods and results sections (<i>e.g.</i> inconsistencies in the numbers of animals in different groups) could be an example of indirect evidence;
		--	There is direct evidence that loss of animals was unacceptably and not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of attrition or exclusion includes: reason for loss is likely to be related to true outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for loss across study groups
5	Domain: Detection Can we be confident in the exposure characterisation?	++	There is direct evidence that exposure was consistently administered (<i>i.e.</i> with the same method and time-frame) across treatment groups. Consistent feed consumption would be an additional element to consider when rating this question.
		+	There is indirect evidence that exposure was consistently administered (<i>i.e.</i> with the same method and time-frame) across treatment groups. For dietary exposure studies, between-group differences in feed consumption would be an additional element to consider when rating this question.
		-	There is indirect evidence that exposure was not consistently administered (<i>i.e.</i> with the same method and time-frame) across treatment groups. For dietary exposure studies, between-group differences in feed consumption would be an additional element to consider when rating this question.
		--	There is direct evidence that exposure was not consistently administered (<i>i.e.</i> with the same method and time-frame) across treatment groups. For dietary exposure studies, between-group differences in feed consumption would be an additional element to consider when rating this question.
6 Key question C	Domain: Detection Can we be confident in the outcome	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes, AND that the outcome was assessed at the same length of time after initial exposure in all study groups.

	Assessment?	+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes,</p> <p>OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results, which is more likely to apply to objective outcome measures. For some outcomes, particularly histopathology assessment, outcome assessors are not blind to study group as they require comparison to the control to appropriately judge the outcome, but additional measures such as independent review by trained pathologists can minimize this potential bias,</p> <p>AND there is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed at the same length of time after initial exposure in all study groups,</p> <p>OR it is deemed that assessment of the outcome at a different length of time after initial exposure among study groups would not appreciably bias results.</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors to infer the study group prior to reporting outcomes without sufficient quality control measures</p> <p>OR that the outcome was assessed at a different length of time after initial exposure among study groups</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors or length of time after exposure for outcome assessment (record "NR" as basis for answer).</p>
		--	<p>There is direct evidence for lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors, including no blinding or incomplete blinding without quality control measures</p> <p>OR that the outcome was assessed at a different length of time after initial exposure among study groups.</p>
7	Domain: Selective reporting Were all measured outcomes reported?	++	<p>There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported. This would include outcomes reported with sufficient detail to be included in meta-analysis or fully tabulated during data extraction and analyses had been planned in advance.</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol,</p> <p>OR methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported,</p> <p>OR analyses that had not been planned in advance (<i>i.e.</i> retrospective unplanned subgroup analyses) are clearly indicated as such and it is deemed that the unplanned analyses were appropriate and selective reporting would not appreciably bias results (<i>e.g.</i> appropriate analyses of an unexpected effect). This would include outcomes reported with insufficient detail such as only reporting that results were statistically significant (or not).</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported,</p> <p>OR and there is indirect evidence that unplanned analyses were included that may appreciably bias results,</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about selective outcome reporting (record "NR" as basis for answer).</p>

		--	There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (apical and intermediate) outlined in the protocol, methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported. In addition to not reporting outcomes, this would include reporting outcomes based on composite score without individual outcome components or outcomes reported using measurements, analysis methods or subsets of the data (<i>e.g.</i> subscales) that were not pre-specified or reporting outcomes not pre-specified, or that unplanned analyses were included that would appreciably bias results.
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Appendix D – Methods for reporting the data from the included studies

937 It is anticipated that data will be synthesised for each relevant outcome, building on the measured results for each endpoint considered.

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939 **Table D.1** Study summary table – human studies

Ref. ID (Author, year)	Health Outcome/ Endpoint	Study design	Subjects	Exposure	Results	Relevance to the sub-question	Internal validity

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941 **Table D.2** Study summary table – animal studies

Ref. ID (Author, year)	Health Outcome/Endpoint	Animal species/Strain	No of animals/ group	Exposure (Route, period, duration of administration)	Treatment groups and BPA dose(s) (mg/kg bw per day)	HED	Results	Relevance to the sub-question	Internal validity

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